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XOTIRA TO'G'RISIDA UMUMIY TUSHUNCHA

Mamatqulova Hurriyatxon Husanboyevna

Namangan viloyati

"University of business and science"

universiteti 3-kurs talabasi

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada xotira aslida nima ekanligi va xotira haqida umumiy ma'lumotlar va shuningdek eslab qolishning turlari haqida kengaytirilgan holatda umumiy ma'lumotlar keltirilib o'tilgan. Xotira haqida bir nechta olimlarning fikrlari ham keltirilib o'tilgan.*

Kalit So'zlar: *Xotir, idrok, eslab qolish, eslab qolish metodikalari.*

ОБЩЕЕ ПОНЯТИЕ О ПАМЯТИ

Маматкулова Хурриятхан Хусанбоевна

Наманганская область

«Университет бизнеса и науки»

студент 3 курса университета

Аннотация: *В этой статье представлен расширенный обзор того, что на самом деле представляет собой память, а также общая информация о памяти, а также о типах припоминания.*

Ключевые Слова: *Память, восприятие, запоминание, способы запоминания.*

GENERAL CONCEPT OF MEMORY

Mamatkulova Hurriatkhan Husanboyevna

Namangan region

"University of business and science"

3rd year university student

Abstract: *This article provides an expanded overview of what memory actually is and general information about memory, as well as types of recall. The opinions of several scientists about memory have also been cited*

Key Words: *Memory, perception, memorization, memorization methods.*

KIRISH

Xotira- idrok etilgan narsa va hodisalarni yoki o'tmish tajribalarni esda qoldirish va zarur bo'lganda tiklashdan iborat psixik jarayon. Xotira eng yaxshi damlarni esda qoldiradi. U nerv sistemasi xususiyatlaridan biri bo'lib, tashqi olam voqealari va organizm

reaksiyalari haqidagi axborotni uzoq saqlash hamda uni ong faoliyatida va xulq, xatti harakat doirasida takroriy qobiliyatida namoyon bo'ladi.

Xotira individning o'z tajribasida esda olib qolishi, esda saqlashi va keyinchalik uni yana esga tushirishi xotira deb ataladi.

Xotira haqidagi dastlabki ilmiy qarashlar Sharq mutafakkirlari va yunon faylasuflari (Aristotel va boshqalar) da uchraydi. Xususan, Farobiy Xotiraga bilishdagi aqliy jarayonning tarkibiy qismi sifatida qarab, xotirani faqat insonga emas, hayvonga ham xos xususiyat ekanini alohida ta'kidlagan.

Xotiraning fiziologik asosi bosh miya yarim sharlari po'stlog'ining muvaqqat bog'lanishi (qarang Assotsiatsiya) va ularning keyingi faoliyatidan iborat. Xotira ko'lami, axborotlarning uzoq vaqt va mustahkam saqlanishi, shuningdek, muhitdagi murakkab signallarni idrok etish va adekvat reaksiyalarda ishlab chiqish bosh miya nerv hujayralari (neyronlar) sonining ko'payib borishi hamda uning strukturasi murakkablashuvi jarayonida o'sib boradi. Fiziologik tadqiqotlarda qisqa va uzoq muddatli xotiralar qayd etilgan. Qisqa muddatli xotirada axborotlar bir necha daqiqadan bir necha o'n minutgacha saqlanadi, neyronlar ishiga xalal berilganda (masalan, elektr shok, narkoz ta'sirida) u buziladi. Uzoq muddatli xotirada axborotlar odam umri bo'yi saqlanib turli ta'sirlarga chidamli bo'ladi. Qisqa muddatli xotira asta sekin uzoq muddatli xotiraga aylanadi. Xotira ruhiyatning o'tmish holati bilan hozirgi holati va kelgusidagi holatlarga tayyorlash jarayonlari o'rtasidagi o'zaro aloqadorlikni ko'rsatadi. Boshqa psixik hodisalar kabi xotira ham shaxsning xususiyatlari, uning ehtiyoji, qiziqishlari, odati, fe'l-atvori va shu kabilar bilan uzviy bog'liq.

Xotira namoyon bo'lishdagi shakliga ko'ra, shartli ravishda emotsional xotira (his-tuyg'uni esda tutish), obraz xotirasi (narsalarning tasviri va xususiyatlarini esda tutish), so'z-mantiq xotirasi (narsalarning mohiyati, mazmunini so'z bilan ifodalangan holda esda tutish) kabi turlarga bo'linadi. Bulardan insonda so'z-mantiq xotirasi yetakchi o'rin tutadi. Xotiraning barcha turi bir-birlari bilan chambarchas bog'liq holda kechadi. Psixologiyada, shuningdek, ixtiyoriy va ixtiyorsiz xotiralar farq qilinadi. Ixtiyoriy xotirada muayyan materialni esda olib qolish oldindan maqsad qilib qo'yiladi; ixtiyorsiz xotirada bunday maqsad bo'lmaydi — biror faoliyatda (mas, mehnat jarayonida yoki kim bilandir suhbatlashib turilganda) o'z-o'zidan esda saqlab qolinadi. Barqarorligi jihatdan ixtiyoriy xotira ixtiyorsiz xotiradan samaraliroq.

Fanda xotira bilan bog'liq ravishda unutish masalasini o'rganishga ahamiyat berilmoqda. „Normal“ unutishni psixik kasalliklardagi xotira buzilishidan farq qilmoq kerak. Bu kasalliklarda xotira susayishi (gipomneziya), yo'qolishi (amneziya) yoki bir tomonlama kuchayishi (giperamneziya) kuzatiladi. Ba'zi kasalliklarda u sifat jihatdan buziladi: bemorga bo'lmagan voqealarni go'yoki o'z boshidan kechirgandek tuyuladi, yoki qachonlardir bo'lib o'tgan voqealarni kecha yoki bugun ro'y bergan deb o'ylaydi (konfabulyatsiya, psevdoreminnsensiya), Bunday soxta xotiralar kishida jiddiy ruhiy xastaliklar oqibatida kelib chiqadi. Bunday kasalliklarga bosh miya qon tomirlari aterosklerozi, shikastlanish, miyaga qon quyilishi holatlari, og'ir zaharlanishlar oqibati

(mas, alkogolizm da uchraydigan psixoz) va shu kabilar kiradi. Xotira buzilganda uni keltirib chiqaruvchi asosiy kasallikni davolashga e'tiborni qaratish kerak.

TADQIQOT METADOLOGIYASI

Biz sezgan, idrok qilgan narsalar iz qoldirmasdan yo'qolib ketmaydi, balki ma'lum darajada esda olib qolinadi, ya'ni esimizda saqlanib qoladi va qulay sharoitda yoki kerak bo'lganda esimizga tushadi. Shuningdek, kechirilgan tuyg'u, fikr va qilingan ish-harakatlarimiz ham esimizda saqlanib qoladi va keyinchalik esimizga tushadi. Buni har kim o'z tajribasidan yaxshi biladi. Masalan, o'quvchilar maktabda o'qitilayotgan narsalarini esda olib qoladilar, esda saqlaydilar va esga tushiradilar.

Kundalik tajribamiz ko'rsatadiki, esda qolgan narsalar-ning hammasi ham esimizga tushavermaydi, ularning bir qismi unutiladi. Unutish ham xotiraga oid hodisadir.

Tassurotlarning ana shunday esda qoldirish va keyin esga tushirishning fiziologik asosi muvaqqat nerv bog'lanishlaridir, bu muvaqqat bog'lanishlarning hosil bo'lish, mustahkamlanish va keyin jonlanish (tiklanish) jarayonidir.

Esda qoladigan narsa xotira materialini, esda saqlanib turadigan va esga tushiriladigan narsa esa xotiraning mazmunini tashkil qiladi.

Eng avval bevosita idrok qilingan narsa va hodisalar (uylar, ko'chalar, daraxtlar, hayvonlar va hokazolar)ning obrazlari esda olib qolinadi, saqlanib qoladi va esga tushadi. Ko'rgan badiiy surat va rasmlar, eshitgan muzika kuylari, ashulalar va hokazolar esda qoladi. Ilgari idrok qilingan narsalarning esimizga tushgan ob-razlari tasavvur deb ataladi. Bu xotiramizda saqlanib qolgan idrok obrazlari bo'lib, mazmunan obrazli xotiraga taalluqlidir. Odam xotirasining asosiy mazmunini nutq-so'z materialini tashkil etadi. Idrok qilingan narsa va hodisalarning nomlari, o'qilgan tekstlar, so'zlar, gaplar boshqalarning nutqi esda olib qolinadi, esda saqlanib qoladi va esga tushiriladi. Lekin nutq esda olib qolinganda u yoki bu oddiy tovushlar birikish sistemalari emas, balki nutqda ifodalangan ma'no, o'zi va boshqalarning fikrlari esda qoladi, saqlanadi va esga tushadi. So'zlarning ma'no jihatdan mantiqiy sur'atda bir-biriga bog'lanib esda qolishi va esga tushishi mazmunan so'z-logik xotirasi bo'lib, obrazli xotira-ga nisbatan, ancha murakkab aqliy faoliyatdir. Biz ko'ngildan kechirgan tuyg'ular, har xil muskul va ish - harakatlari ham xotira mazmunini tashkil qiladilar.

Shu sababli esda qoladigan materialning xilma-xil mazmuniga qarab, xotirani, odatda, obrazli, so'z logik, emotsional (tuyg'u-hissiyot) va harakat xotirasi kabi xillarga aj-ratiladi. Albatta, xotiraning ana shu xillarga bo'linishi nisbiydir. Xaqiqatda xotiraning shu hamma xillari bir-biri bilan chambarchas bog'langan, birona narsaning esimizda qolgan va keyin esimizga tushirilgan obrazi gap bilan ifodalanadi, har bir tuyg'u-hissiyot birona bir tasavvurga, yoki fikrga, yoki ish-harakatga va hokazolarga bog'liq holda tug'iladi.

MAVZUGA OID ADABIYOTLAR SHARXI

Kishining boshqa odam yoki narsa haqidagi biror taassurotni esda saqlash, eslab qolish qobiliyatiga xotira deyiladi. Insonning o'ylash, fikrlash qobiliyati ham xotiraga kiradi. Biror kishi uchun qilinadigan izzat-hurmat ham xotira hisoblanadi. Marhumlar eslansa, arvo h xotira bo'ladi. Xayoli sochilgan, fikri tarqoq kishiga nisbatan "parishonxotir" iborasi qo'llanadi. Xotira inson avval o'zlashtirgan, his qilgan, bajargan, o'ylagan narsalarni

bosh miyada saqlash va zarur bo‘lganda tiklash qobiliyatidir. Xotira bois kishilar to‘plagan tajribalari, bilimlarini esda olib qoladi, qo‘llaydi, kelajak avlodga qoldiradi. Ko‘pchilik umuman barcha narsani unutmaslikni istaydi. Biroq bu insonga juda og‘irlik qiladi. Yaxshi xotira esda qolishi zarur voqea-hodisalarni esda saqlashgina emas, balki kerak bo‘lmagan narsalarni unuta bilish hamdir. Shuning uchun ham yaxshi eslab qolishning asosiy sharti – o‘ylash. Nimalarni eslab qolganini o‘ylash, yodda qolayotgan narsani avvaldan ma’lum narsa bilan bog‘lash, eslab qolayotgan narsalarni fikran ko‘ra bilish lozim. Eng muhimi, eslab qolayotgan narsa qachon va nima uchun zarur bo‘lishi mumkinligi haqida o‘ylash kerak. Xotira uzoq davr bilishning umumiy muammolari bilan uzviy bog‘liq ravishda asosan falsafada o‘rganildi. Xotira haqidagi dastlabki ilmiy qarashlar Sharq mutafakkirlari va yunon faylasuflari ta’limotlarida uchraydi. Xususan, Forobiy xotirani bilishdagi aqliy jarayonning tarkibiy qismi sifatida qarab, uning faqat insonga emas, hayvonga ham xos xususiyat ekanini alohida ta’kidlagan. Zamonaviy psixologiyada xotira atrof muhitdagi voqelikni bevosita va bilvosita, ixtiyorsiz va ixtiyoriy ravishda, passiv va aktiv holda, reproduktiv va produktiv tarzda, verbal va noverbal shaklda, mantiqiy va mexanik yo‘l bilan aks ettirgan holda esda olib qolish, esga tushirish, unutish hamda tanish, eslashdan iborat ruhiy jarayon sifatida talqin qilinadi. Ixtiyoriy xotirada muayyan materialni esda olib qolish oldindan maqsad qilib qo‘yiladi. Ixtiyorsiz xotirada bunday maqsad bo‘lmaydi va u biror-bir faoliyatda (masalan, mehnat jarayonida yoki kim bilandir suhbat paytida) o‘z-o‘zidan esda saqlab qolinadi. Barqarorligi jihatdan ixtiyoriy xotira ixtiyorsiz xotiradan samaraliroq. Shu bilan birga, alohida va umumiylik namoyon qiluvchi ijtimoiy hodisa, barcha ta’sirlarni ijodiy qayta ishlashga yo‘naltirilgan xotira mavjud.

Xotirani quyidagi muhim mezonlarga muvofiq turlarga ajratish mumkin:

1. Ruhiy faoliyat faolligiga ko‘ra: a) harakat yoki motor harakat xotirasi; b) obrazli xotira; v) his-tuyg‘u yoki hissiyotsi; g) so‘zmantiq xulosasi. Bulardan so‘z-mantiq xotirasi yetakchi o‘rin tutadi. Xotiraning barcha turi bir-biri bilan bog‘liq holda kechadi.
2. Ruhiy faoliyat maqsadiga binoan: a) ixtiyorsiz; b) ixtiyoriy; v) mexanik xotira
3. Ruhiy faoliyat davomiyligiga ko‘ra: a) qisqa muddatli; b) uzoq muddatli; v) operativ xotira.

Kundalik hayotda xotira asosan ikki turga – uzoq muddatli va qisqa muddatli xotiralarga bo‘linadi. Qisqa muddatli xotiralar hatto bir soniya ichida gavdalanib, shu ondayoq esdan ko‘tarilishi mumkin. U asta-sekin uzoq muddatli xotiraga aylanadi. Uzoq muddatli xotiralar esa kishi yodida bir umr saqlanib qolishi mumkin. U insonning hayot tajribasidagi mushtaraklik, uyg‘unlik va barqarorlikdan dalolat beradi.

XULOSA

Umimiy xulosaga keladigan bo‘lsak, Xotira ruhiyatning o‘tmish holati bilan hozirgi va kelgusidagi holatlarga tayyorlash jarayonlari o‘rtasidagi o‘zaro aloqadorlikni ko‘rsatadi. Boshqa psixik hodisalar kabi xotira ham shaxs xususiyatlari, uning ehtiyoji, qiziqishlari, odati, fe’l-atvori bilan bevosita bog‘liq. Insonning o‘zligi uning xotiralari majmuida mujassam bo‘ladi. Inson xotirasi bilan insondir. Xotirasiz kishi esa odamiylikdan chiqadi. Insonning xotirasi bo‘lmasa, u o‘z kelajagini qanday tasavvur qiladi? Agar xotira bo‘lmasa,

ota-bobolarimiz to‘plagan kerakli bilim va tajribalarni bilmasdan, har kuni, har qadamda yangi-yangi muammo va g‘ov-to‘siqlarga duchor bo‘lar edik... Odamzod o‘zining kechagi kunini xotirlay olsagina, o‘tmishdan zarur saboq va xulosalar chiqarib, ongli hayot kechirishi mumkin.

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THE IMPORTANCE OF GROUP WORK FOR STUDENTS

Xaldurdiyeva O'g'iljeren Abajan qizi,
Student of Uzbekistan state world languages university,
Philology faculty;
Usmonova Shahodat Abdurahimovna
Scientific adviser, (PhD) Associated Professor;

Abstract: *In this article there is given thorough information about the significance of team work for a student, its role in the classroom, in which aspects of life it can help students, and what qualities people can grow by working in a group.*

Key words: *group work, individual task, team work, broadening horizon, critical thinking, competitiveness, collaboration, self-esteem, language acquisition, boosting vocabulary, self-development, shared ideas, acceptability, better memory, different prospective, interactions,*

INTRODUCTION

Sometimes accomplishing the task on your own feels easier than doing it with a company. It can be efficient somehow: you can work in your own time, and can control the whole process. However, when students are asked to choose one mode of working - a group or an individual task - comparatively high percentage of them would go for the first one. For years it has been observed by experts that either a group work is important in learning or working individually. While there are several strong points of an individual work, numerous reasons of working with a team have been seen and proved.

5 main advantages of group activities

1. Broadening horizons. When we are required to work in a team we have to discuss a topic, negotiate how to address it with others, and have to listen to other members' ideas as well as expressing ourselves. Their ideas can make an impact on our thinking and help us broaden our horizons by exchanging our perception on the topic. Because, while listening to others we have to compare, contrast and integrate different thoughts into ours. Someone's thinking perhaps shows us our weak point and as a result we can enhance our knowledge and sharpen our perspectives

2. Improving self-esteem. Collaboration with fellow members will give a positive feeling of being included. It will help overcome shyness that few students feel when required to respond, and create self-esteem. If the students are confident in their productive work they will directly make themselves feel happy and satisfied.

3. An active memory. The researches conducted by experts Barkley, Cross and Major in 2005 and by Davis in 1993 suggest that people often tend to memorize things discussed in a team rather than reading or listening to them alone. Because our brain gets active during group discussions as we try to do our best for a successful result.

4. Beneficial in career growth. Being a team member is one of the top soft skills which any big corporate company requires and values. Learning to adapt to news and to listen to

others, and communicate effortlessly in any group shows that you can manage other people and bring a positive impact to the company, also ensuring harmony.

5. Better acceptability. Sometimes it feels merely frustrating that final result of the group project is not exactly what we want. It is hard for any perfectionist to accept ideas and perspectives in a group assessment submission that we do not agree and support are the best. However, this outcome makes us feel proud because we are seeing a good result. As a result we shape a sense of shared ownership.

The role of team work in the classroom.

1. Improving critical thinking and competitiveness. During the lesson if students are divided into groups by teachers to accomplish the task they will do their best. Because they must address the solution and think of a solution to deliver results better than the rest of the groups. This situation will lead the students to think critically which is very beneficial for their growth, and build competitiveness which always encourages them to be successful.

2. Time-saving for teachers. It's always easier for teachers to evaluate students as a group rather than conducting activities that require doing it individually. Teachers can also delegate the evaluation task to the students, making it a peer evaluation process. The benefit of this practice is that students will understand what standards are expected from them and how they can justify the scores they have marked for their peers.

3. Boosting vocabulary. In any language learning process, communication and interaction with others are widely considered as the best ways of learning. Because we will hear others languages, and it gives us a chance to learn new words, to use them in contests, to hear new ideas about topic, and to compare them with ours, and unless we do not understand we can easily ask (as some students feel shy when they do not get what a teacher says and do not ask). By this way, we can remember much more vocabulary and how to use them.

Conclusion

As mentioned above group activities give a number of opportunities to the group members in terms of emotional self-development, adaptability, memory, language acquisition, shared ideas, different prospective. All in all, team work leads students to gain several soft skills that will open doors to the bright career path, and will help them with various aspects of life.

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ENERGIYA ISTE'MOLI BINOLARIDA QAYTA TIKLANUVCHI ENERGIYA MANBALARINI JORIY ETISHNING EKOLOGIK AHAMIYATI

Murtazoyev Firdavs Feruz o'g'li

*Buxoro muhandislik – texnologiya instituti, Elektr va energetika muhandisligi kafedrasida o'qituvchi
stajyori.*

Energiya, atrof – muhit va barqaror rivojlanish o'rtasida chambarchas bog'liqlik mavjud. Barqaror rivojlanishga intilayotgan jamiyat faqat atrof – muhitga ta'sir ko'rsatmaydigan energiya manbalaridan foydalanishi kerak. Biroq, barcha energiya resurslari atrof – muhitga ma'lum darajada ta'sir ko'rsatganligi sababli, atrof – muhitga ajratadigan chiqindilari va ularning salbiy ta'siri tufayli barqaror rivojlanishga qo'yiladigan cheklovlarga zid bo'ladi. Birlashgan Millatlar Tashkiloti tomonidan ishlab chiqarilgan “Barqaror rivojlanish maqsadlari (BRM)”ga muvofiq dunyo aholisini toza va arzon energiya bilan ta'minlanishi (BRM7), iqlim o'zgarishi va uning oqibatlariga qarshi kurashish (BRM13) maqsadlarida energiya ishlab chiqarishning atrof-muhitga ta'sirining naqadar dolzarbligini isbotlab turibdi. BRMning yuqoridagi ikki maqsadiga erishishning eng oson usuli bu – energiya samaradorlikni oshirish va qayta tiklanadigan energiya manbalaridan foydalanish ekologik barqarorlikka erishishning eng tez va arzon usuli ekani ta'kidlaydi. Energiya samaradorlik, qayta tiklanuvchi energiya manbalari va ekologiya o'rtasida bog'liqlik mavjud, chunki bir xil xizmatlar yoki mahsulotlar uchun resurslardan kamroq foydalanish va ifloslanish odatda energiya samaradorligini oshirish yoki yoqilg'idan olinadigan energiya ulushini kamaytirish bilan bog'liq. Ushbu maqolada keltirilgan o'rganishlar:

- a) yoqilg'idan foydalanib olinadigan energiyadan foydalanish natijasida ozon qatlamining yemirilishi va issiqxona effekti nuqtai nazaridan atrof – muhitga ta'sirining har tomonlama muhokamasi;
- b) energiyani tejash nuqtai nazaridan mavjud ekologik muammolarning ba'zi yechimlari ayniqsa qayta tiklanadigan energiya texnologiyalari joriy etish;
- c) energiya samaradorligini oshirish bo'yicha ba'zi nazariy va amaliy cheklovlar;
- d) energiya va barqaror rivojlanish, atrof – muhit va barqaror rivojlanish o'rtasidagi munosabatlarni muhokama qilinadi.

Shu munosabat bilan energetika, atrof-muhit va barqaror rivojlanish bilan bog'liq bir qator masalalar bo'yicha respublikamizdagi islohotlarning ham hozirgi, ham kelajak istiqbollari nuqtai nazaridan ko'rib chiqamiz.

Shuningdek, respublikamizda ishlab chiqarilayotgan elektr energiyaning 85 %i IESlarida asosan tabiiy gaz yoqish (93%), ko'mir va neft qoldiqlarini yoqish orqali hosil qilinmoqda. 2019-yilda O'zbekistonda yoqilg'i yonishi natijasida CO₂eq chiqindilari 109,6 million tonna CO₂ ni tashkil etdi. Elektr va issiqlik ishlab chiqarish umumiy hajmning 41% ni tashkil etdi va uy xo'jaliklari ikkinchi yirik emission manba (23%), transport (14%) va

sanoat (11%). Qolgan emissiyalar xizmatlar (6%), qishloq xo‘jaligi va energetika sanoati (6%) hissasiga to‘g‘ri keladi.

2013 – yilda dastlabki “Muqobil energiya manbalarini yanada rivojlantirish chora-tadbirlari” to‘g‘risida prezident qarori asosida quyosh fotoelektrik stansiyalarni loyihalashtirish va ularni qurish bo‘yicha yirik loyihalar amalga oshirilishi boshlandi. 2019 – 2030 yillarga mo‘ljallangan yashil iqtisodiyotga o‘tish strategiyasining asosiy maqsadi uzoq muddatli barqaror iqtisodiy rivojlanishga erishish va O‘zbekiston tomonidan 2018 yilda ratifikatsiya qilingan Parij kelishuvi bo‘yicha O‘zbekiston majburiyatlarini bajarishdan iborat. Jumladan, strategiyada 2030-yilgacha YaIM birligiga to‘g‘ridan – to‘g‘ri 2010– yil bilan solishtirganda 10% ga issiqxona gazlarini kamaytirish; energiya samaradorligi ko‘rsatkichini ikki baravar oshirish va YaIMda CO₂ chiqarishni kamaytirish; energetika tizimida qayta tiklanuvchi energiya manbalari ulushini umumiy energiya ishlab chiqarishda 25% dan yuqoriga yetkazish belgilangan.

Shunga muvofiq aholi, ishlab chiqarish korxonalari va davlat korxonalari hamda tashkilotlari tomonidan mikrogrid tizimini joriy etish bo‘yicha qator loyihalar bosqichma – bosqich amalga oshirilmoqda. PQ-57-son qarorga muvofiq “Qayta tiklanuvchi energiya manbalarini va energiya tejovchi texnologiyalarni joriy etishni jadallashtirish chora-tadbirlari” to‘g‘risida rag‘batlantirish mexanizmlari ishlab chiqildi.

Qarorga muvofiq o‘rnatilgan quyosh panellarining ishlab chiqarish quvvati korxonaga elektr energiya iste‘molidagi o‘rnini 1 – jadvalga keltirilgan energiya iste‘moli obyektlari kesimida ko‘rishimiz mumkin.

1 – jadval

Energiya iste‘moli obyektlarida quyosh panellarini o‘rnatishning ahamiyati

Quyosh panellari o‘rnatilgan obyekt	O‘rnatilgan quvvati, kVt	Generatsion quvvati, kVt/(10 oy)	Tabiiy gaz, m ³	Tabiiy gaz ajratmalari, kg CO _{2eq}	Ko‘mir, kg	Ko‘mir ajratmalari, kg CO _{2eq}	Daraxtlar soni, 10 yil (1x1x167kg)
Amir textile	300	280000	83587.4	183892.3	182000	440440	373
Buxoro muhandislik texnologiya instituti	60	67000	17332	38130.4	43550	97552	81

Jadvaldan ko‘rinib turibdiki, quyosh panellaridan foydalanishning nafaqat davlatimiz iqtisodiyotiga, balkim tabiiy resurslardan foydalanishni kamaytirish natijasida zararli gazlar miqdorini ham kamaytirib ekologik muvozanatni ta‘minlash imkoniyati mavjud.

Xulosa o‘rnida shuni aytish joizki, energiya resurslari va ulardan foydalanish barqaror rivojlanish bilan chambarchas bog‘liq. Jamiyatlar barqaror rivojlanishga erishishlari yoki unga erishishga harakat qilishlari uchun nafaqat barqaror energiya resurslarini topishga, balki ushbu resurslardan foydalanish jarayonlarining energiya samaradorligini oshirishga ham katta kuch sarflash kerak. Bundan tashqari, atrof-muhit muammolarini hal qilish lozim. Ushbu maqola orqali qayta tiklanuvchi manbalardan foydalanish:

- issiqxona gazlari chiqindilarini barqarorlashtirish yoki kamaytirishga erishish uchun o‘zining ulushini qo‘shadi;
- energiya iste‘molchilarining energiya samaradorligini oshirishda va elektr ta‘minoti ishonchligi ko‘rsatkichini yaxshilash imkonini beradi.

COMMON CHALLENGES OF TRANSLATION

Ubaydullayeva Begoyim O'ktamjon qizi

Andijan State Institute of Foreign Languages

Faculty of English philology, teaching methodology, and translation studies

Student of group 407

Annotation: *The article deals with the problem of teaching: This article will focus on difficulties or obstacles frequently encountered in the translation process. These challenges may be experienced across various languages and contexts. Indicates that the challenges discussed are specifically related to translating text from one language to another. This could include written documents, spoken language, or multimedia content.*

Keywords: *Language nuances, cultural context, idioms and expressions, ambiguity, tone and register, technical terminology, syntax and structure, translating humor, contextual meaning.*

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada tarjima jarayonida tez-tez uchrab turadigan qiyinchiliklar yoki to'siqlarga e'tibor qaratilgan bo'lib, bu qiyinchiliklar turli tillarda va kontekstlarda uchraydi. Muhokama qilingan muammolar matni bir tildan ikkinchi tilga tarjima qilish vazifasi bilan bog'liqligini ko'rsatadi. Bu yozma hujjatlar, og'zaki til yoki multimedia kontentini o'z ichiga oladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Til nuanslari, madaniy kontekst, idioma va iboralar, noaniqlik, ohang va registr, texnik terminologiya, sintaksis va tuzilish, yumorni tarjima qilish, kontekstual ma'no.*

Аннотация: *В данной статье речь пойдет о трудностях или препятствиях, которые часто встречаются в процессе перевода. С этими проблемами можно столкнуться на разных языках и в разных контекстах. Указывает на то, что обсуждаемые проблемы конкретно связаны с задачей перевода текста с одного языка на другой. Это могут быть письменные документы, устная речь или мультимедийный контент.*

Ключевые слова: *Языковые нюансы, культурный контекст, идиомы и выражения, двусмысленность, тон и регистр, техническая терминология, синтаксис и структура, переводческий юмор, контекстуальное значение.*

Translating accurately involves more than just substituting words. Challenges include preserving tone, idiomatic expressions, cultural nuances, and context, which vary greatly between languages. Additionally, some concepts or words may not have direct equivalents in the target language, requiring creative solutions. Maintaining clarity while staying faithful to the original meaning is key. Below are the most common problems that a translator may encounter while translating from one language to another :

The first: is cultural nuances: Translators must navigate the cultural differences between languages to accurately convey the intended meaning of the source text. Sometimes, translating words related to a nation's mentality or its own culture is challenging because an issue or a word completely does not exist in another one. Take the

example of ta'lim va tarbiya . They have different meanings in Uzbek culture but we can only translate it to English as the education.

The second is ambiguity: Some words or phrases may have multiple meanings in different languages, leading to potential confusion or misinterpretation. There is an example of ambiguity in a multicultural setting where both English and Spanish are spoken. The word "mole" presents a perfect example of ambiguity:

English (mole - animal): In English, "mole" refers to a small burrowing mammal with velvety fur, typically found in gardens. Spanish (mole - sauce): In Spanish cuisine, "mole" (pronounced mo-leh) is a rich, savoury sauce made with chilli peppers, spices, chocolate, and sometimes nuts or fruit. In a conversation where someone mentions "mole," depending on the language context, it could lead to confusion. For instance, if someone says, "I love mole," an English speaker might think they're referring to the animal, while a Spanish speaker would understand it as the sauce. This difference in interpretation could potentially lead to miscommunication or at least a moment of confusion until the context clarifies which "mole" is being referred to.

The third: is idioms and colloquialisms: Expressions unique to a particular language or region can be challenging to translate accurately without losing their original meaning. Take the example of the English idiom It rains cats and dogs. That can be challenging to translate into Uzbek. A translator should find a fitting equivalent like : Paqirlab yog'moq.

The fourth is technical terminology: Translating specialized or technical content requires a deep understanding of the subject matter to ensure accuracy and clarity.

The fifth is tone and style: Maintaining the appropriate tone and style of the original text can be difficult, especially when translating creative or literary works.

The sixth is time constraints: Meeting tight deadlines while ensuring quality translations can be a major challenge for translators, especially when working on large projects.

The seventh is localization: Adapting content for specific regions or target audiences requires a nuanced understanding of cultural norms, preferences, and language variations.

The eighth is quality control: Ensuring consistency, accuracy, and coherence throughout a translation project can be challenging, especially when multiple translators are involved.

The ninth is technology limitations: While translation tools and software can aid the translation process, they may not always provide accurate or contextually relevant translations.

The last is client expectations: Managing client expectations and feedback can be challenging, as different stakeholders may have varying preferences or requirements for the translated content.

Translation poses several challenges, including preserving the original meaning, cultural nuances, idiomatic expressions, and context. Maintaining tone, style, and the intended emotional impact can also be difficult. Additionally, dealing with ambiguous or untranslatable words and phrases presents a challenge. Moreover, linguistic differences

such as syntax, grammar, and word order between languages can complicate the process. Lastly, meeting deadlines while ensuring accuracy adds pressure on translators.

In conclusion: Common challenges of translation include linguistic nuances, cultural differences, idiomatic expressions, and technical terminology. Despite these hurdles, accurate translation requires a deep understanding of both the source and target languages, along with context and subject matter expertise. Ultimately, successful translation hinges on the translator's skill in conveying the intended message faithfully while preserving the tone and meaning of the original text.

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SEMIZLIKNI TURLI FENOTIPLARIDA YURAK QON-TOMIR KASALLIKLARINI KELIB CHIQISH XAVFI PROGNOZI

Majidov Sharifjon Xusenovich
Osiyo xalqaro universitetida Assistent

Anatatsiya: Semizlik- hozirgi kunda eng muhim tibbiy- ijtimoiy muammoga aylangan bo'lib, Jahon sog'liqni saqlash tashkilotining ma'lumotiga ko'ra, ortiqcha vazn va semizlik bilan muammolari bo'lgan insonlarning 44-57% ida Qandli diabet (II-tip), 17-23% Yurak ishemik kasaligi, 17% arterial gipertenziya, 30% o't-tosh kasaligi, 14 % osteoartrit, 11% ida xavfli o'smalar kelib chiqish xavfi yotadi. Bularni hammasi insonlarning hayot sifati buzilishi va erta mehnat qobiliyatidan ayrilishiga olib keladi. Shunday xavfli oqibatlar asosida Semizlik hozirgi kunda sog'liqni saqlash va Ijtimoiy sohadagi eng muhim muammolardan biriga aylangan.

Kalit so'zlar: Metabolik sog'lom semizlik, Metabolik nosog'lom semizlik, HADS shkalasi, depressiya, xavotirlik.

Maqsad: Semizlikni turli fenotiplarida metabolik o'zgarishlarni bemorning psixo-emotsional holatiga ta'sirini HADS shkalasi orqali baholash va taqqoslash

Tadqiqot: Yurak qon tomir tizimida kuzatiladigan quyidagi: birinchi paydo bo'lgan stenokardiya, infarkt miokard, to'satdan yurak o'limi, surunkali yurak yetishmovchiligi, aterosleroz, essensial arterial gipertoniya kabi kasalliklarda kelib chiqishga asosiy sabab bo'luvchi omil bu organizmdagi metabolik moddalar almashinuvini buzilishi yotadi. Metabolik moddalar almashinuvini buzilishi barcha semiz insonlar o'rtasida ham kuzatilmaydi. Shunga ko'ra Semizlik 2 turdagi fenotipga ajratilgan:

- Metabolik sog'lom semizlik
- Metabolik nosog'lom semizlik
- Kasalxonatashvishvadepressiyashkalasi HADS (The hospital Anxiety and

Depression Scale Scale Zigmond A.S., Snaith R.P.) (1-jadval) umumiy tibbiy amaliyotda depressiya va xavotirni birlamchi aniqlash uchun ishlab chiqilgan. xavotirlik va depressiya darajasini aniqlash uchun HADS shkalasi bemorga qiyinchilik tug'dirmaydi va natijalarni to'ldirish va sharhlash uchun uzoq vaqt talab qilmaydi. HADS klinisyenga bemorning hissiy holati va farovonligini yaxshiroq tushunishga yordam berish uchun mo'ljallangan.

Amaliy tavsiyalar. O'lchov 10-15 daqiqada mustaqil ravishda, hech kim bilan muhokama qilmasdan bajarilishi kerak. Javoblar barcha elementlar uchun tanlanishi kerak. HADS shkalasi bo'yicha har bir bayonotda to'rtta javob variant mavjud. Oxirgi 7 kun ichida sizning holatingizga mos keladigan javobni tanlang va belgilang. Savolga javob berish haqida uzoq o'ylamang. Sizning birinchi reaksiyangiz eng to'g'ri bo'ladi.

Shkala 14 punktdaniboratbo'lib, uning “xavotir” va “depressiya” uchun belgilangan punktlari mavjud:

Xavotir qismi (toqraqamlar

— 1, 3, 5, 7, 9, 11, 13)

Depressiya qismi (juftraqamlar

— 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14).

Javoblar varianti: 0 – belgiyo‘q; 1 –yengil; 2 – o‘rtacha; 3 – og‘ir; 4 – o‘taog‘ir.
Demak, ballarda rajasining oshib borishi depressiya va xavotir darajasi oshib borayotganini ko‘rsatadi.

Ballar yig‘indisi:

0-7

— me‘yor (xavotir va depressiya yo‘q);

8-10

— subklinik xavotir va depressiya;

11 va undan yuqori – kuchli xavotir va depressiya

Таблица 1. HADS: каждому утверждению соответствуют 4 варианта ответа; выберите тот из ответов, который соответствует Вашему состоянию, а затем просуммируйте баллы в каждой части		
Часть I (оценка уровня тревоги)		Часть II (оценка уровня депрессии)
1. Я испытываю напряжение, мне не по себе все время часто время от времени, иногда совсем не испытываю	3 2 1 0	1. То, что приносило мне большое удовольствие, и сейчас вызывает у меня такое же чувство определенно, это так наверное, это так лишь в очень малой степени, это так это совсем не так
2. Я испытываю страх, кажется, что что-то ужасное может вот-вот случиться определенно это так, и страх очень велик да, это так, но страх не очень велик иногда, но это меня не беспокоит совсем не испытываю	3 2 1 0	2. Я способен рассмеяться и увидеть в том или ином событии смешное определенно, это так наверное, это так лишь в очень малой степени, это так совсем не способен
3. Беспокойные мысли крутятся у меня в голове постоянно большую часть времени время от времени и не так часто только иногда	3 2 1 0	3. Я испытываю бодрость совсем не испытываю очень редко иногда практически все время
4. Я легко могу присесть и расслабиться определенно, это так наверно, это так лишь изредка, это так совсем не могу	0 1 2 3	4. Мне кажется, что я стал все делать очень медленно практически все время часто иногда совсем нет
5. Я испытываю внутреннее напряжение или дрожь совсем не испытываю иногда часто очень часто	0 1 2 3	5. Я не слежу за своей внешностью определенно, это так я не уделяю этому столько времени, сколько нужно может быть, я стал меньше уделять этому времени я слежу за собой так же, как и раньше
6. Я испытываю неусидчивость, мне постоянно нужно двигаться определенно, это так наверно, это так лишь в некоторой степени, это так совсем не испытываю	3 2 1 0	6. Я считаю, что мои дела (занятия, увлечения) могут принести мне чувство удовлетворения точно так же, как и обычно да, но не в той степени, как раньше значительно меньше, чем обычно совсем так не считаю
7. У меня бывает внезапное чувство паники очень часто довольно часто не так уж часто совсем не бывает	3 2 1 0	7. Я могу получить удовольствие от хорошей книги, радио- или телепрограммы часто иногда редко очень редко
Общее количество баллов		Общее количество баллов
Интерпретация результатов: 0-7 баллов – «норма» (отсутствие достоверно выраженных симптомов тревоги и депрессии), 8-10 баллов – «субклинически выраженная тревога/депрессия», 11 баллов и выше – «клинически выраженная тревога/депрессия».		

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BOSHLANG'ICH SINF O'QUVCHILARINI SO'Z BOYLGINI OSHIRISHDA DIDAKTIK O'YIN TEXNOLOGIYALARI

Mamadjanova Shoxida Nemat qizi
University of Business and Science. O'qituvchi

Annotatsiya: Maqolada kichik maktab yoshidagi o'quvchilarning ingliz tilida og'zaki va yozma nutqda leksik ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishga qaratilgan didaktik o'yinlar taqdim etilgan; ularning funksiyalari va chet tilni o'qitish-tarbiya jarayonidagi roli aniqlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: didaktik o'yin, o'yin usuli, leksik ko'nikma, boshlang'ich ta'lim o'quvchilari, kommunikativ kompetensiya.

Annotation The article presents didactic games aimed at developing lexical skills in oral and written speech in English for elementary school students; their functions and role in the process of teaching and educating a foreign language are identified.

Keywords: didactic game, game method, lexical skill, elementary school students, communicative competence.

Аннотация: В статье представлены дидактические игры, направленные на развитие лексических навыков в устной и письменной речи на английском языке у учащихся начальной школы; определены их функции и роль в процессе обучения и воспитания иностранному языку.

Ключевые слова: дидактическая игра, игровой метод, лексический навык, учащиеся начальной школы, коммуникативная компетенция.

KIRISH

O'quvchilarning kommunikativ kompetensiyasi tarkibida leksik kompetensiyani shakllantirish jarayonini faol o'rganish va tasvirlashga qaramasdan, ko'pgina o'qituvchilar hanuzgacha zamonaviy o'quvchilarning qiziqish va ehtiyojlarini hisobga olmagan holda eski usul va texnologiyalardan foydalanishda davom etmoqdalar. Maktab sharoitida dasturiy leksik materialni o'zlashtirish chet tillarni o'qitishda leksik ustunlik printsipiga muvofiq amalga oshirilishi mumkin, bu esa chet tilni o'qitishda leksik jihatga alohida e'tibor qaratilishi kerakligini nazarda tutadi, insonlar o'rtasidagi muloqot aynan leksika orqali va uning asosida amalga oshiriladi. N.N. Gez ham shu nuqtai nazarni qo'llab-quvvatlaydi va leksik vositalar orqali fikrlarni shakllantirish, ifoda etish va rasmiylashtirish jarayonlari bilan so'zni qabul qilish va ishlatish yaqinidan bog'liqligini ta'kidlaydi. O'quvchilar faol va qiziqish bilan ishlaydilar, bir-birlariga yordam beradilar, do'stlarini diqqat bilan tinglaydilar, o'qituvchi esa ularning o'quv faoliyatini boshqaradi.

Til fonetik, leksik va grammatik vositalardan iborat murakkab ko'p qirrali tuzilma hisoblanadi. Har bir turdagi til vositalari muhim va qolganlari bilan birgalikda o'rganilishi kerak. Grammatikani ko'pincha tilning "skeleti" deb atashadi, ammo bu jihatni egallash insonning chet tilini bilishini anglatmaydi. Leksik mazmunsiz grammatik tuzilmalarning hech qanday ma'noviy yuklamasi yo'q. Buning sababi shundaki, nutqning leksik tomonini

egallashning asosiy vazifalaridan biri atrof-muhitdagi predmet va hodisalarni nomlash (nominativ funksiyasi) hisoblanadi. O'quvchilar muvaffaqiyatli bo'lishlari uchun chet tilini muloqot vositasi sifatida qo'llash va o'z fikrlarini erkin ifoda etish uchun o'quv jarayonida leksik ko'nikmalarni rivojlantirish zarur. Leksik ko'nikmalarni shakllantirish faqat alohida so'zlarning ma'nolarini bilish bilan cheklanmaydi va o'quvchining o'rganilgan leksik birliklarni turli nutq faoliyat turlarida qo'llash qobiliyatini nazarda tutadi. O'quvchi nafaqat kerakli leksik birliklarni uzoq muddatli xotiradan "chaqira" olishi, balki ularni o'z fikrini ifodalash uchun kommunikativ maqsad va nutqiy vaziyatga muvofiq qo'llashi kerak [2, s. 85].

Zamonaviy metodik adabiyotlarda o'yin usuli tushunchasi uchraydi. An'anaviy o'qitish usullari bilan solishtirganda, o'yin usuli ishtirokchilarning yuqori faolligi bilan ajralib turadi. Muhimi shundaki, o'yin usuli ayniqsa leksik ko'nikmalarni egallashning boshlang'ich bosqichida samarali hisoblanadi. Bu o'qitish jarayonida tabiiy kommunikativ vaziyatlarni tashkil etishga imkon beradi. A.N. Shchukin yangi leksik birliklarni samarali o'rganish uchun o'quvchilarning o'quv faoliyatini faollashtirishga qaratilgan o'yin usullaridan foydalanish kerakligini ta'kidlaydi.

O'yin usullarini chet tilini o'qitish jarayonida qo'llash bir qator muhim metodik vazifalarni bajarishga, o'quvchilarning yangi materialni qabul qilishga psixologik tayyorgarligini oshirishga yordam beradi. Shuningdek, bu yangi til materialini ko'p marta o'zlashtirish va mashq qilish uchun tabiiy vaziyat yaratadi.

O'quv jarayonining tarkibiy qismi bo'lgan o'yinlar zamonaviy kommunikativ yondashuv sharoitida alohida ahamiyat kasb etadi, bunda, S.A. Pavliashviliyning fikricha, ular quyidagi funksiyalarni amalga oshiradi:

- o'quvchi xotirasi, diqqatini rivojlantirish, ma'lumotni qabul qilish, shuningdek, umumiy o'quv ko'nikma va malakalarini rivojlantirish bilan bog'liq o'quv funksiyasi;
- o'yin sherigiga nisbatan diqqatli va insonparvar munosabat sifatlarini tarbiyalashga qaratilgan tarbiyaviy funksiyasi;
- o'quvchilarning shaxsiy imkoniyatlarini faollashtirish maqsadida shaxsiy sifatlarini uyg'un rivojlantirishga qaratilgan rivojlantiruvchi funksiyasi;
- chet tilida muloqot muhiti yaratish, jamoani birlashtirish, shuningdek, o'yin ishtirokchilari o'rtasida yangi emotsional-kommunikativ munosabatlarni o'rnatishga qaratilgan kommunikativ funksiyasi;
- o'quvchilarning asab tizimiga yuklama tufayli yuzaga kelgan emotsional zo'riqishni bartaraf etuvchi relaksatsion funksiyasi [4, s. 107].

O'yin jarayonida o'quvchilarda mustaqil ishlash ko'nikmalari va ma'lumotni tasniflash va tahlil qilish qobiliyati shakllana boshlaydi, shuning uchun dars o'tkazishda o'yinlarga alohida e'tibor berish juda muhimdir.

Didaktik o'yinlar o'quvchilarning dunyoqarashini kengaytirish, bilim faoliyatini shakllantirish, amaliy faoliyat uchun zarur bo'lgan ko'nikma va malakalarni rivojlantirish, chet tilini o'qitish jarayonini faollashtirish uchun qo'llaniladi. Ular nutqiy muloqot muhitini yaratishga yordam beradi, o'quvchilarning faol nutqiy-fikrlash faoliyatini rag'batlantiradi. Oddiy o'yinlardan farqli o'laroq, "didaktik o'yinlar o'quv-bilim yo'nalishiga ega" [9, s. 159].

Bizning fikrimizcha, didaktik o'yin aniq belgilangan o'quv maqsadi va unga mos natijaga ega bo'lgan muhim xususiyatga ega, bu natijalar asoslanishi, aniq ko'rinishda ajratilishi mumkin, ya'ni didaktik o'yinda va uning yordamida o'yinchilar nimanidir o'rganishlari kerak.

Ijtimoiylashtiruvchi o'yinlar ushbu madaniyatning me'yorlari va qadriyatlarini singdiradi, o'quvchini yangi ijtimoiy muhit me'yorlariga moslashtiradi. Algoritmli o'yinlar o'yin vaziyatida belgilangan qat'iy harakatlar ketma-ketligi bilan ajralib turadi. Shartli-kommunikativ o'yinlar o'quvchilarning kommunikativ yo'nalishi bilan tavsiflanadi, bu esa o'qituvchi tomonidan belgilangan nutqiy vaziyatda amalga oshiriladi. Haqiqiy-kommunikativ o'yinlar o'quvchilarning nutqiy faoliyatda yuqori darajadagi mustaqilligi va ijodiy xarakteri bilan ajralib turadi. Muallifning fikricha, bu turdagi o'yinlarni "leksika yetarlicha yaxshi o'zlashtirilgan bosqichda qo'llash kerak" [7, s. 40-41].

Hozirgi vaqtda, axborot texnologiyalarining rivojlanishi va video o'yinlarning paydo bo'lishi bilan, chet tilini o'qitishda kompyuter texnologiyalaridan foydalanish bilan o'yinlar ommalashmoqda. Interaktiv doska yordamida amalga oshiriladigan interaktiv o'yinlar faol qo'llanilmoqda. Umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablarida SMART board interaktiv doskalari ommalashmoqda, ular SMART Notebook dasturi orqali ishlaydi. Ushbu doska universal bo'lib, 2 ta ish rejimini nazarda tutadi: kompyuter sichqonchasi yordamida yoki sensorli ekranda stilus yordamida ishlash rejimi.

O'yin jarayoni: O'qituvchi mavzuni tanlaydi. Ekranda turli ob'ektlar joylashgan sharlar paydo bo'ladi. Dastur so'zni aytadi, uni sharlar orasidan topish kerak. O'yinchining vazifasi so'zning tovushli obrazini grafik bilan moslashtirishdir.

Shartli-kommunikativ o'yinlar: "Voyante" o'yini, leksik birliklarni faollashtirish maqsadida. Bir vaqtning o'zida 3 o'quvchi doskada o'ynashi mumkin. Bir sinovdan muvaffaqiyatli o'tgandan so'ng, boshqa o'quvchini o'yinga taklif qilish mumkin. O'yinni chorak yoki o'quv yilining oxirida o'tkazish mumkin, chunki leksika mavzular bo'yicha taqsimlanmagan, balki o'tilgan materialni faollashtirishga qaratilgan. Shuningdek, jamoaviy o'yin shakli ham mumkin.

O'yin jarayoni: O'quvchi o'zining jodugar / sehrgar ismini yozadi. Keyin ekranda xarita va o'yinchi o'tishi kerak bo'lgan sinovlar paydo bo'ladi. Har bir muvaffaqiyatli o'tilgan sinovdan so'ng, o'yinchi o'yin oxirida eliksir tayyorlash uchun bir element oladi. Sinovlar turli xil bo'lishi mumkin. Masalan, o'rmon maxluqi bilan jang: zarba paytida ekranda leksik mashq paydo bo'ladi va ovoz topshiriqni aytadi. O'yinchining vazifasi belgilangan vaqt ichida to'g'ri javob yozishdir. Agar javob to'g'ri bo'lsa, o'yinchiga ball beriladi va raqibning hajmi kichrayadi. Jang raqib yo'q bo'lib ketguncha yoki, masalan, kichik zararsiz hayvonga aylanguncha davom etadi. G'alabadan so'ng, jodugar / sehrgar eliksir elementlarini izlashda davom etadi.

Haqiqiy-kommunikativ o'yinlar: "Un bonhomme" o'yini, o'quvchilarning xotira va diqqatini rivojlantirish, "Qish" mavzusidagi leksik birliklarni faollashtirish maqsadida; jamoada yoki individual ravishda amalga oshirilishi mumkin; tanlangan mavzu bo'yicha leksik ko'nikmalarni shakllantirishning yakuniy bosqichida o'tkazilishi kerak.

O'qituvchi o'yin darajasini tanlaydi (jami 4 ta). Ekranida matn paydo bo'ladi. Masalan, qorbobo nima kiygan. O'quvchilarning vazifasi tavsifni eslab qolishdir. Keyin ekranida oq qorbobo paydo bo'ladi, uni ko'rsatmalarga muvofiq kiyintirish kerak. Ekraning chap tomonida qorboboning tana qismlari taklif etiladi, ularni o'zgartirish kerak (sharf, oyoq, ko'zlar va h.k.). O'yinchilarning vazifasi qorboboni eslab kiyintirishdir. Keyin valider tugmasini bosish va o'yinchilar topshiriqni to'g'ri bajarganligini tekshirish kerak.

O'quvchilar faol va qiziqish bilan ishlaydilar, bir-birlariga yordam beradilar, do'stlarini diqqat bilan tinglaydilar, o'qituvchi esa ularning o'quv faoliyatini boshqaradi.

XULOSA

Chet tillarni o'qitish jarayonida o'yinlarning o'rni va roli juda muhimdir. Didaktik o'yinlar o'quvchilarning bilim olish qiziqishlarini shakllantirishga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi, chet tilini ongli ravishda o'zlashtirishga yordam beradi. Ular mustaqillik, tashabbuskorlik, jamoada ishlash qobiliyatini rivojlantirishga yordam beradi. O'quvchilar faol va qiziqish bilan ishlaydilar, bir-birlariga yordam beradilar, do'stlarini diqqat bilan tinglaydilar, o'qituvchi esa ularning o'quv faoliyatini boshqaradi. O'yinlar yordamida o'quvchilarning o'quv motivatsiyasini oshirish mumkinligi ko'rsatadi. Shu sababli, didaktik o'yinlar chet tillarni o'qitishda samarali vosita sifatida keng qo'llanilishi kerak.

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**DEVELOPMENT OF FINANCIAL STATEMENTS OF BUDGET
ORGANIZATIONS**

**BYUDJET TASHKILOTLARINI MOLIVAVIY HISOBOTLARINI ISHLAB
CHIYISH**

Atamurotova Gulchehra Mamatmo`minovna

Bank-moliya akademiyasi 70412201

Davlat moliyaviy nazorati va auditi yo`nalishi magistratura tinglovchisi

Annotatsiya. O'zbekiston Respublikasining iqtisodiyoti bozor munosabatlarini erkinlashtirish yo'li orqali rivojlanmoqda. Bu jarayonlarda tashkilot va muassasalarni boshqarish, uning oldiga qo'yilgan reja ko'rsatkichlariga doir vazifalarni bajarish maqsadida xo'jalik faoliyati ustidan kundalik kuzatib borishni talab qiladigan hamda uning amaliy ahamiyatini asoslashga xizmat qiladigan tavsiya va xulosalar mazkur maqolada shakllantirilib chiqilgan. Bunday kuzatish va boshqarish xo'jalik hisobini barqarorlashtirish yuzasidan muammolarga yechim va takliflar keltirib o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: xo'jalik hisobi, miqdor, qiymat o'lchovi, hisob ko'rsatkichlari, moddiy o'lchov, tovar moddiy qiymatliklar.

Bozor iqtisodiyoti sharoitida xo'jalik hisobi har bir faoliyat turi egalari tomonidan o'zining xohishiga qarab tashkil qilinib, umumbelgilangan talablarga rioya qilish bilan birga boshqarishning ma'muriy - buyruqbozlik tizimiga xos bo'lgan qat'iy tartibga solingan hisobning o'rniga davlat tomonidan qo'yiladigan tartibotini minimumgacha kamaytirib boradi.

Xo'jalik hisobining umumiy uslubiy asoslariga rioya qilish sharoitida, uning nafaqat shakllari va tashkil qilinishi har xil bo'lmay, xattoki, hisob ko'rsatkichlarini olish uslubiyati ham har xil bo'lishi mumkin. Natijada xar xil mulk egalari ixtiyorida bo'lgan tashkilot va muassasalardagi bir xil turdagi ko'rsatkichlar har xil yo'l bilan ishlab chiqilishi mumkin, lekin e'lon qilinadigan hisobotdagi ma'lumotlarning solishtiruvchanligini ta'minlash uchun moliyaviy hisobga ilova qilingan tushuntirish xatida tashkilot va muassasalar tomonidan qabul qilingan hisob siyosati haqida izohlar keltirilishi kerak.

Buxgalteriya hisobida xo'jalik operatsiyalari o'lchov obekti bo'lib hisoblanadi. Ular tashkilot va muassasalarning moliyaviy ahvoriga ta'sir qiladigan xo'jalik hayotining hodisalaridir. Xo'jalik hisobi tomonidan qamrab olinadigan ob'ektlar raqam ko'rsatkichlari vositasida aks ettiriladi. Ularni olish uchun xo'jalik hisobida moddiy, mehnat va qiymat o'lchovlari qo'llaniladi.

Tashkilot va muassasalarning xo'jalik faoliyati ustidan rahbarlik qilish hamda xo'jalik jarayonlarini boshqarish maqsadida axborotlarni olish uchun faqat kuzatuvni amalga oshirishning o'zi kifoya qilmaydi. Olingan ma'lumotlarni o'lchash, ya'ni mutaxassislarga zarur bo'lgan ma'lum bir miqdoriy ko'rsatkichlarda ifodalash lozim bo'ladi. Undan so'ng bu ko'rsatkichlar boshqarishga zarur bo'lgan yo'nalishda axborotni guruhlash, tashkilot va

muassasalar faoliyatini keyinchalik baholash va axborotning saqlanishini ta'minlash hamda ichki auditni tashkil qilish maqsadida hisobning tegishli registrilarida ro'yxatga olinishi lozim.

Demak, hisob deganda olingan ma'lumotlardan ma'lum bir amaliy yoki ilmiy maqsadlarda keyinchalik foydalanish uchun yoki boshqa voqealar, harakatlar, dalillarni qayd etishni tushunmoq kerak.

Bundan tashqari, nizomda hisob-kitob hujjatlarini rasmiylashtirish va ularni ijro qilish, memorial orderlar bilan hisob-kitoblar, to'lov topshiriqnomalari bilan hisob-kitoblar, to'lov talabnomalari bilan hisob-kitoblar, inkasso topshiriqnomalari bilan hisob-kitoblar, akkreditivlar bo'yicha hisob-kitoblar, cheklar bilan hisob-kitoblar, bank tomonidan emissiya qilingan, personalizatsiyalangan, to'lov vositasi sifatida ishlatiladigan va o'z saqlovchisiga bank hisob-varag'idagi mablag'lari doirasida operatsiyalarni, jumladan, hisobvaraqa orqali naqd pulsiz hisob-kitoblar, yuridik shaxsni qayta tashkil etish va tugatish vaqtida mablag'larni hisobdan chiqarish qoidalari haqida batafsil yoritilgan.

Shulardan kelib chiqib biz xo'jalik buxgalteriya hisobi - bu faoliyat ko'rsatayotgan subyektning mulki, majburiyatlari, xo'jalik operatsiyalari va ularning harakatini yoppasiga hamda uzluksiz hujjatlashtirish yo'li bilan tartibli yig'ish, nazorat qilish, o'lchash, ro'yxatga olish, pul o'lchovida ishlov berish tizimidir degan xulosani berishimiz mumkin.

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**DETERMINATION OF MICROFLORA PRESENT IN MANUSCRIPTS
PRESERVED IN HISTORICAL MONUMENTS**

S.F. Abdulloeva

PhD student,

Samarkand State University, Samarkand

B.I. Turaeva

doctor of philosophy of biological sciences,

Institute of the Microbiology, Academy of Sciences of the Republic Uzbekistan, Tashkent

Abstract: *This study provides insights into the various microorganisms that can damage manuscripts stored in historical monuments. The microbial communities responsible for deteriorating cultural heritage sites are described.*

Keywords: *microbiome, microbial damage, microflora, micromycete, bacteria, historical manuscripts.*

Аннотация: *Данное исследование дает информацию о различных микроорганизмах, способных повредить рукописи, хранящиеся в исторических памятниках. Описаны микробные сообщества, наносящие ущерб объектам культурного наследия.*

Ключевые слова: *микробиом, микробное повреждение, микрофлора, микромицет, бактерии, исторические рукописи.*

Cultural heritage serves as a testament to human history, preserving the historical essence of civilizations. Historical monuments and museums conduct extensive scientific research and educational efforts, including the collection, study, storage, and restoration of valuable items. Manuscripts, textiles and artifacts from historical monuments play a crucial role in maintaining the original cultural heritage of each region and country. However, many microbiological issues stem from improper environmental conditions for storing and displaying manuscripts within historical monuments. Factors such as fluctuations in temperature and relative humidity, exposure to light, dust, inadequate storage and substandard display methods contribute to the deterioration of these manuscripts[2].

Globally, research is underway on the protection of cultural heritage. Scientists working on preservation emphasize that sampling should be conducted based on specific measurement protocols. It is necessary to install photocatalytic ionizers and air purification systems with controlled microclimates in exhibition rooms, eliminate pathogenic heterotrophic bacteria, prevent contamination from microflora proliferating due to anthropogenic activities, and develop countermeasures. However, preventing and controlling microbial damage to ancient manuscripts presents several challenges [5]. To ensure these historical materials endure for future generations, it is crucial to develop new technologies and systematic approaches for their preservation [4]. Advances in biotechnology have enabled microbiologists to create methods to combat harmful

microorganisms. Prevention of microbial damage to archaeological, organic, and inorganic objects is also being addressed through new research techniques. To determine the biological systems and metabolic processes of microorganisms damaging ancient manuscripts in cultural heritage sites, measures must first focus on identifying the pathogenic microflora and developing antagonistic microorganism strains against them. For the effective preservation of cultural heritage, interdisciplinary collaboration between microbiologists, geologists, chemists, archaeologists, and ecologists is essential and should be systematically implemented [6]. The biological systems and metabolic processes of microorganisms contribute to the biological deterioration, loss, and weakening of natural materials and structures, as well as discoloration and loss of ethnographic deposits. Researchers from various fields, including microbiology, geology, chemistry, physics, archaeology, and ecology, have initiated studies to preserve cultural heritage for future generations. Supporting the science of heritage conservation is crucial for protecting these invaluable assets. Understanding the mechanisms of microbial communities allows for the effective selection of appropriate storage methods [5]. Artifacts can be categorized based on their material composition and production processes. Organic artifacts, which make up a large portion of objects displayed in museums worldwide, are particularly prone to deterioration. However, microbial attacks can accelerate this process, with varying effects depending on the materials involved [2]. The primary difference between the degradation rates of inorganic and organic artifacts lies in the degree of quality loss. According to Gioventu, bacteria play a significant role in the mineralization process and the breakdown of complex organic molecules (such as carbohydrates, proteins, lipids, and cellulose), which leads to the completion of the organic cycle. Various microbial species found in typical museum environments have specific preferences for materials like glue, cellulose, and protein [4].

Artifacts made from different materials possess unique characteristics, making them more susceptible to damage. Physical properties such as the presence of ink and pigments on the surface can accelerate the deterioration of paper artifacts, highlighting the importance of remediation techniques. The degradation of historical manuscripts is often linked to the activity of hydrolytic enzymes like cellulase, amylase, gelatinase, and pectinase, which cause biological deterioration. Archaeological data must be carefully preserved for future generations, as these materials are essential for deepening our understanding of culture and heritage [5].

A large number of fungal infections are found in manuscripts. It should be noted that *Aspurgillus* sp., *A. furrigati*, and *A. circumdati* are signs of environmental potential. It is caused by the storage and use of manuscripts in the wrong ecological environment [3].

Historical monuments-manuscripts, printed documents, books and others of historical value from ancient times to the present play an important role in preserving the classical original cultural heritage of every country and region. changes in internal temperature and relative humidity, exposure to light, installation of photocatalytic ionizers and microclimate-controlled air purification systems in exhibition rooms, elimination of pathogenic heterotrophic bacteria, reproduction by various anthropogenic anthropogenic

activities researches are being carried out aimed at the implementation of a number of works, such as the prevention of infection with pathogenic microflora and the development of countermeasures.

In order to strengthen the protection of the objects of material cultural heritage in the Samarkand region, it is important to determine the microflora that harms the ancient manuscripts stored in the monuments, determine the antagonistic microorganisms to this pathogenic microflora and the optimal measures to fight against the pathogenic microflora. Based on microbiotechnology, it is recommended to carry out control measures using biological methods, to determine the optimal control measure.

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CONCEPT OF MODALIZATION OF WORD GROUPS IN ARABIC AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

Diyora Mirakhatova

Doctoral student, TSUOS, Uzbekistan

Annotation: *In this article, concept of modalization of word groups in Arabic and Uzbek languages, which belong only to that language and have such characteristics that one does not meet in the other, are analyzed.*

Key words: *concept of modalization, Arabic and Uzbek languages, noun category, possessive and conjunctive suffixes.*

INTRODUCTION

When talking about common signs of word groups in Arabic and Uzbek languages, the signs common to both languages are: noun word group, adjective word group, verb word group, number. The existence of categories such as verbs and verbs in both groups divides word categories into three groups only in Arabic, and all categories except verbs are studied in the noun category. Here, let's look at the aspects of nouns in Arabic and Uzbek that are common to both languages: In Arabic, in some cases, verbs are formed from the stem, in some cases, nouns are formed and in turn, verbs can be formed from them, and finally, both nouns and verbs can be formed from some stems at the same time. In Uzbek, a noun is a group of words that denote the name of an object.

What is noun? What? Your questions will be answered.

The noun is used with possessive and conjunctive suffixes, singular and plural. In the sentence, the noun is the main part, the secondary part, and also the impulse, for example:

1. My mother works in the factory.
2. Don't leave today's work for tomorrow!
3. Young people help the elderly.

In the first sentence, my mother is the noun, in the second sentence, the noun of work is a complement, and in the third sentence, the noun of youth is an imperative. In the Arabic language, nouns can be in agreement, and in the Uzbek language, nouns with singular, dual, and plural forms are classified as follows. It is divided into relative, proper noun, diminutive and caressing nouns, object name, locative noun, abstract noun, compound noun, double noun.

Main part: In Arabic, nouns are nouns and nouns, diminutives and nouns of caress, once the name of an action. (إِسْمُ الْمَرَّةِ) (عِلَّةٌ دَرِبَةٌ) 1 time to strike, (وَإِدْعَاءٌ) 1 time to promise (وَإِدْعَاءٌ) 1 time to run) type of action بِعِيسٍ style of walking (عِلَّةٌ) (النَّوْعُ إِسْمٌ) write meaning name style, a noun denoting a type of action made from 4-stem and polysyllabic stems corresponds to a noun denoting action 1 time.

Uzbek and Arabic languages also have a grammatical number category. It is known that in the Uzbek language there are singular and plural numbers of nouns. In the Uzbek language, the plural number of nouns is formed by adding – s plural.

In addition, things that can be measured, (substances) for example: honey, oil, salt, silver, gold, iron, tea, flour and abstract nouns: love, conscience, patience, etc.

In the Uzbek language, the plural suffix – s, is also used to express respect. There is no Arabic binary number in Uzbek. It is represented by 2 words in Uzbek language. There are 6 consonants in the Uzbek language. These are: beginning, ending, pointer, time of place, departure and exit agreements. Among these conjugations, the main conjugation has no morphological indicator.

In the Arabic language, there are 3 concordances (head, case, focus) and all of them have a morphological indicator.

The verb in the Uzbek language is similar to the verb in the Arabic language in terms of its function. Arabic and Uzbek languages also have a set of verbs, and their common features are: verbs are in the person-number, tense category, proportion, inclination, participle, infinitive, and transitive forms. In both Arabic and Uzbek, verbs change person, tense, and number. There are past and present forms of verbs. When pronouncing verbs in Uzbek, personal tense suffixes are added only after the verb. In Arabic, the present tense is represented by prefixes and suffixes of person and number. There are 3 declensions in Uzbek, and 5 declensions in Arabic. Both languages have transitive and intransitive verbs. In Uzbek, the verb is formed in two ways - morphological and syntactic, in Arabic it is formed only morphologically.

Conclusion: In the Arabic and Uzbek languages, we can say that the special features of the word groups belong only to that language and have such characteristics that one does not meet in the other. From these features, we can get a binary category that is unique only to the Arabic language. This category, which is not found in other languages, is used in Arabic when the grammatical binary number refers to two objects or events, and it is formed as follows

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THE BASICS OF STYLISTIC DEVICES IN ENGLISH LITERATURE

Dilnoza Umurzakova

Senior teacher, Academic lyceum of Uzbek State World Languages University, Uzbekistan

Annotation : *In this article, the basics of stylistic tools in English literature is given information about the extremely complex whole, which can freely combine various styles at the discretion of the author and which has the characteristic of giving people aesthetic pleasure.*

Key words: *English literature, Artistic work, writing style, philosophical observation, state of mind, author-narrator.*

INTRODUCTION

The artistic text, as is known, is formed based on the requirements and patterns of the artistic style, therefore poetic, romantic, and solemn forms of expression are widely used in it. The choice of words, the structure of sentences, the use of lexical-semantic, rhythmic-intonational units also come from the requirements of this style. Among the linguistic features of the literary text, the most important thing is that emotional words, slang words, historical and archaic words, slang and slang, figurative words, words with the same meaning, similar in form, words with a similar pronunciation and opposite meaning, as well as units such as a phrase, are given a lot of space. It should be emphasized that any text is a unique system.

But the structure of the text is fundamentally different from the structure of the sentence. The syntactic pattern of the sentence is stable, formed over centuries, easily used by everyone and almost unchanging. The speaker or the author uses these patterns voluntarily according to his intention. The situation in the text is different.

Main part: Artistic style is the main means of artistic perception of reality and its expression. The artistic style is also remarkable for the fact that it embodies the possibility of expressing a person's character, his inner world, mental states, various events in nature with all their complexity. The most characteristic feature of artistic speech style is imagery and emotionality. If the scientific method expresses generalized concepts with fixed, special terms and formulas, the artistic method has the ability to describe the most subtle points of the human heart and nature with the help of its reserve words. In the artistic style, the author effectively and creatively uses the visual means of the language in order to enhance the aesthetic effect of the work, and also creates new forms of words and expressions. Therefore, in this style, writers are not limited to using existing words. For skilled writers, the available language vocabulary is always a limited resource. They are in the process of creating new individual words and phrases.

In artistic speech, the language serves to create a unique image, character, realistic landscape, and to show high imagery. Other stylistic materials can be freely used in artistic speech according to the author's intention. In this style, each writer differs from one another depending on the scope of artistic perception of reality, creative potential, expressive skills, and compositional formation of the text. Accordingly, artistic speech style

is a form of speech that has wider possibilities than others, is very comprehensive and rich in visual means of expression. Artistic text is created in the style of artistic speech. Depending on how the artistic speech is told by the author in the work, we can get an idea of the writer's thinking, writing style, and philosophical observation. According to the artistic and aesthetic intention, the author sometimes holds the reins of the narrative in his own hands, sometimes hands it over to the characters, and sometimes hands it over to another narrator. As a result, a multifaceted picture-narrative speech - a polyphonic speech, which does not bore the reader and can expand the content of realism.

Conclusion: The language of a work of art is interesting and impressive, depends on the correct selection of language units, the compatibility with the content of the text, and the speech of the author-narrator. In the author's speech, one can feel the way of observing reality from the outside, openly or secretly expressing one's attitude to the described events. If the author has a positive attitude towards the hero, we can feel the author-narrator's goodwill towards him in the image.

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TYPES OF ECONOMIC GROWTH

Ismoilova Madina

Nukus branch of the Tashkent University of Information Technologies
named after Muhammad al-Khorezmi, Republic of Uzbekistan

In some countries, economic development is at a very high pace, and in others it is the opposite. Types of economic growth in order to understand how to accelerate economic growth, the level of real GDP (that is, real GDP per capita) and its rate of change between countries and the factors influencing it will need to be studied. Raising production and potential GDP, which is the main driver of economic growth, largely depends on the amount of resources and the duration of their quality.

Economic growth is divided into two types: 1) extensive; 2) intensive. Growth due to increase in quantity of resources or slow increase of economic factors belongs to the type of extensive growth of this economy. We will consider these factors in detail below. The use of new scientific and technical achievements, further improvement of the quality of resources, development based on new technologies is an intensive type of economic growth. Accordingly, economic growth is divided into two groups based on two types of factors:

□ Factors affecting the number of resources include: land area, labor activity, type of business and capital. Extensive growth factors include: to increase the labor force, to build a new enterprise, to increase the amount of production equipment, to attract additional land to the farm, to expand the use of new land and to effectively use the extraction of minerals, to further develop foreign trade in order to increase the amount of raw materials and others. However, the experience and skills of workers, the productivity of labor, the quality of production equipment and technologies will not be updated. Therefore, the income from the product per unit of labor and capital remains unchanged;

□ Factors affecting quality. Factors of the intensive type of economic growth include: increasing the level of professional knowledge and professional training of workers; use of relatively improved products and tools used in production; use of new technologies (mainly, resource-saving); scientific, planned organization of work; to use relatively useful and beneficial methods in the way of managing the economy by the state.

Factors of the type of intensive economic growth, the increase of knowledge and skills of members of the society, their accumulation, scientific discoveries and innovations achieved due to new knowledge and factors aimed at their implementation are of great importance. Because it is precisely this scientific and technical knowledge that plays a key role in improving the quality of production tools and manufactured products.

The main economic characteristic of the quality of resources is their productivity. That is, the more resources are effectively used, the more products can be obtained, and at the same time, the quality of the products should not be harmed. The main factor determining the lifestyle of the country's population is labor productivity. Because the more products or services a worker can produce in one hour, the higher the labor productivity and the correspondingly larger real GDP. The standard of living of the population depends

on the amount of goods and services created in the country, therefore, the higher the real GDP of the country, the better the lifestyle of the population.

Also, labor productivity is influenced by the following factors based on economic growth and its pace:

□Physical capital includes buildings, land, technical equipment, and tools used in the production of goods and services. In addition, physical capital itself is the result of production. That is, the more modern and improved it is, the higher the quality of goods and services;

□Human capital (labour capital) is the knowledge, skills and labor skills acquired by members of society during education (school, college, university or vocational schools) and in the process of work (learning by doing). Human capital physical physical capital is the result of the production process, like physical capital, and it also increases the ability of society to create new goods and services;

□Natural resources are the factors that nature provides as a gift, that is, land, rivers, minerals, etc. Forest resources are an example of renewable natural resources (you can plant new ones instead of cut down trees). Non-renewable minerals: oil, coal, iron ore, etc. It will take thousands or millions of years for them to recover. □The reserve of natural factors is not considered the main condition for high rates of economic growth and high efficiency of the economy.

In fact, the rapid pace of economic development in the United States was initially related to the abundance of vacant land, land suitable for agriculture. Kuwait and Saudi Arabia have become the richest countries in the world due to the discovery and production of many oil pipelines. But, for example, although Japan is not rich in natural factors, it has taken a place among the mature and developed countries of the world. South Asian countries, such as Hong Kong, Taiwan, South Korea, and Singapore, are experiencing rapid economic growth not due to the abundance of natural resources. Natural factors are the only factor that cannot be developed by man. Availability of non-renewable resources is the main problem of economic growth. But we can find a solution to such a problem through modern technological discoveries and innovations or find an equivalent option. For example, using plastic materials instead of iron and aluminum products can be a relatively alternative option.

□Technological knowledge - means finding the best methods used in production and being able to use them effectively. The difference between technological knowledge and human capital is that it arises in order to create better, more efficient ways of doing work (it answers the question of how it is produced), and the human factor arises based on the result of testing various methods and experience in the production process.

Technological knowledge is of great importance in economic growth. Because they are the main factor in solving the problem of limited resources.

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TIJORAT BANKLARI KREDIT PORTFELI TAHLILI VA UNI OPTIMALLASHTISH YO'NALISHLARI

Nazarova Xurshida Igamberdiyevna

O'zbekiston respublikasi

Bank-moliya akademiyasi

tinglovchisi

Annotatsiya: Maqolada mamlakatimizdagi tijorat banklarining kredit portfelini samarali shakllantirish, uni optimallashtirish masalalari va iqtisodiyotga yo'naltirilgan kredit qo'yilmalari hajmi, tijorat banklari aktivlari va ularning tarkibida kreditlarning miqdori tahlili o'rganilgan va tegishli xulosalar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: kredit, kredit portfeli, tijorat banklari, optimallashtirish, bank aktivlari, bank kapitali.

Abstract: In the article is studied the issues of effectively strengthening the credit portfolio of commercial banks and the volume of economically oriented banks' credit analysis of the assets of commercial banks and the amount of loans in their structure carried out in the country and are given the corresponding conclusions.

Key words: loan, loan portfolio, commercial banks, optimization, bank assets, bank capital

KIRISH

Bank sanoati dunyodagi yetakchi tarmoqlardan biridir. Tijorat banking asosiy maqsadi foyda olish bo'lgani uchun kredit berish birinchi o'rinda turadi. Tijorat banklarining kreditlari xo'jalik yurituvchi subyektlarning joriy va investision xarajatlarini moliyalashtirish manbalaridan biri bo'lib, iqtisodiyotning barqaror rivojlanishini ta'minlashda muhim o'rin tutadil. Shu bilan birga, raqobat muhitida bank faoliyati nazoratchilari va menejerlari uchun moliyaviy aktivlarni optimal shakllantirish va ularni tog'ri taqsimlash muhim masala hisoblanadi. Tijorat banking kredit portfelini shakllantirish, optimallashtirish va sifatli boshqarish kredit siyosatini amalga oshirishning asosiy bosqichi hisoblanadi. Hozirgi vaqtda kredit portfelining holati nafaqat bankning kredit siyosati sifatini, balki kelgusida bank uchun kredit faoliyati natijalarini prognoz qilish imkonini ham beradi. Tijorat banklarining kredit portfelini to'g'ri shakllantirish, optimallashtirish masalalari va uning tahlili mobaynida bank tomonidan kreditlarning holati, muddati, iqtisodiy sohalar bo'yicha taqsimlanishi, ta'minot turlari, kreditlarning sifati va boshqa ko'rsatkichlar bo'yicha tahlil ishlarining doimiy tarzda olib borilishi, o'z navbatida kredit portfeli sifatiga o'zining ijobiy ta'sirini ko'rsatadi.

Mavzuga oid adabiyotlar tahlili. So'nggi yillarda bank kredit portfelini optimallashtirish va boshqarish usullari bo'yicha turli metodlar ishlab chiqilmoqda. Banklar kredit portfelini shakllantirish to'g'risida qaror qabul qilishlari uchun firmalarning

ehtiyojlari, bozor raqobati va bankning imkoniyatlarini inobatga olishlari zarur (Klaassen, 1998). Tijorat banklarida kredit portfelini optimallashtirishda eng yaxshi amaliyot bank mablag'larini boshqarishning optimal aralashmasini keltirib chiqaradigan tartiblarini aniqlashdir. Tobin izlanishlari natijasiga ko'ra (1965), portfel nazariyasi bank portfelini optimallashtirish va boshqarishda qo'llanilishi mumkin, chunki bank kutilayotgan xavf va likvidlik darajasini hisobga olgan holda aktivlar portfelining daromadlilik stavkalarini maksimal darajada oshirishga intiladi.

Iqtisodchi olimlar Cohen and Hammer (1967) tadqiqotlari natijasiga ko'ra, bank kredit portfelini optimallashtirishda uchta maqsad o'rtasida mos muvozanatni topish

asosiy masala hisoblanadi, bular: rentabellik, likvidlik va xavfsizlik. Umuman olganda, to'rtta asosiy omil banklarning aktivlar portfelini optimallashtirish va boshqarish xattiharakatlariga muhim ta'sir qiladi. Bu omillarga quyidagilar kiradi: a) mamlakatdagi qonunchilik qoidalari, b) depozitlarning xavfsizlik darajasi, d) iqtisodiyotda kreditga bo'lgan talab, e) bank aksiyadorlarining daromadga intilishlari darajasiga bog'liq.

AQSh, Kanada, Angliya va boshqa rivojlangan davlatlarda kredit portfelini saramali shakllantirish va boshqarishda (Credit portfolio management yoki loan portfolio management) ya'ni CPM katta miqdordagi, asosan likvidlilik darajasi past, turli xildagi kreditlarga ega bo'lgan banklar va boshqa moliya institutlari uchun asosiy funksiya hisoblanadi.

Bugungi kunda optimal kredit portfelini shakllantirish bankning muhim vazifalardan va asosiy muammosi hisoblanadi. Har qanday bankning kredit siyosatining yakuniy maqsadi optimal muvofiqlashgan kredit portfelini shakllantirishdir. Mavjud kredit resurslarining miqdori, ularning qiymati, kredit bo'yicha foiz stavkasi, resurslarni jalb qilish shartlari bo'yicha cheklovlar mavjud bo'lgan holatda optimal kredit portfelini shakllantirish muammosi va uni hal qilish bank mutaxassislari uchun asosiy va doimiy yechilishi lozim bo'lgan masala hisoblanadi.

Tahlil va natijalar: Mamlakatimiz tijorat banklari kredit portfelini tahlil qilinganda kreditlarning jami aktivlarga bo'lgan holatini ko'rib chiqish amaliy ahamiyatga ega. Buning natijasida banklarning kredit portfelini qanday shakllangankigi, ularning risklilik, daromadlilik va likvidlilik darajalarini qay darajaliligiga baho beriladi. Quyidagi jadvalda tijorat banklari aktivlari, ularning tarkibida kreditlarning miqdori va ulushi ko'rsatkichlarini xalqaro amaliyotdan kelib chiqib tahlil qilamiz. 1-jadval ma'lumotlariga asosan, tijorat banklari aktivlari 2023-yilda 556,7 trln. so'mni tashkil qilib, 2014-yilga nisbatan 500,5 trln. so'mga ko'paygan, bu tahlil qilinayotgan davr oralig'ida deyarli o'n baravar o'sganligini ko'rsa bo'ladi. Bank aktivlari tarkibida kreditlarning ulushi 2023-yilda 70,1 foizni tashkil qilib, o'tgan yillarga nisbatan ozgina kamayishga ega bo'lgan.

1-jadval

**Tijorat banklari aktivlari va ularning tarkibida kreditlarning
miqdori va ulushi.**

Ko'rsatkichlar	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Tijorat banklari jami aktivlari (trln. so'm)	56,2	65,2	84,1	166,6	214,4	272,7	366,1	444,9	556,7
Kreditqo'yimlari (trln. so'm)	34,5	42,7	53,4	110,6	167,4	211,6	276,9	326,4	390,1
Kredit qo'yimlarining bank aktivlari tarkibidagi ulushi (foiz hisobida)	61,4	65,5	63,5	66,4	78,1	77,6	76,5	73,4	70,1

Iqtisodiyotga yo'naltirilgan kredit qo'yimlari hajmi o'tgan yilga nisbatan 2022- yilda 19,6 foizga oshib, joriy 2023-yil 1-yanvar holatiga 390,1 trln. so'mga yetganligi, hamda kreditlarning YaIM nisbatan darajasi 43,9 foizni tashkil etganligini ko'rishimiz. O'z navbatida, tijorat banklarining kreditlash imkoniyatini yanada oshirish ular kredit portfelining sifatiga bog'liq. Bu o'z navbatida esa, banklar kredit portfelini optimallashtirishga va boshqarish samaradorligini oshirishni taqozo etadi.

Kredit portfelini optimallashtirish kredit portfelining sifati, kredit faoliyati samaradorligi va riskni baholash bo'yicha ishlab chiqilgan usullari bilan bog'liq. Shu bilan birga, har bir bank kredit portfelini optimallashtirishning o'ziga xos usullariga ega va bir-biridan sezilarli darajada farq qilishi mumkin. Tijorat bankining optimal kredit portfelida jalb qilingan resurslar va ularni kreditga joylashtirish jarayonida kreditlar quyidagilarga javob berishi kerak: 1) bank ixtiyorida mavjud kredit resurslari muddati va summasiga javob berishi; 2) daromadlilik darajasi maksimal darajada bo'lishi; 3) risk darajasi minimal maqbul darajaga tushirilishi shart. Kredit portfelini optimallashtirish va sifatli boshqarish kreditlash jarayonida bank faoliyatining tashkil etilishi bo'lib, u kredit riskining oldini olish yoki kamaytirishga qaratilgan. Quyidagi rasmda tijorat banklari kredit portfelini shakllantirish jarayonini ko'rishimiz mumkin bo'ladi.

Tijorat banklari kredit portfelini shakllantirish jarayoni

1. Bankning kredit siyosati maqsadlari va strategiyasigamuvofiq kredit limitlari tizimini shakllantirish

2. Kredit portfelini shakllantirishda alohida kreditlash obyektlari va turlari bo'yicha kredit mablag'lari ajratish

3. Kredit portfelining holati va uni boshqarishni tahlil qilish

Kredit portfelini shakllantirish va uni optimallashtirish bankning kredit faoliyati umumiy maqsadi shakllantirilganda, kredit siyosati strategiyasi ishlab chiqilgandan so'ng boshlanadi. Bugungi kunda banklar o'zlarining kreditlarini faqatgina o'z imkoniyatlaridan kelib chiqqan holda boshqarishlari ancha murakkab bo'lgan masala hisoblanadi. Ularga

o‘zlarining kredit portfelini optimallashtirish va sifatli boshqarilishi uchun boshqa moliya institutlari bilan aloqa o‘rnatishlari ancha yordam beradi. Quyidagi keltirilgan 4-jadvalda tijorat banklarining kredit portfelini optimallashtirishda e‘tibor qaratilishi kerak bo‘lgan muhim holatlarni keltiramiz.

Kredit portfelini optimallashtirishda muhim holatlar

Holatlar	Bank kredit portfeli optimallashtirishdagi qadamlar
1-holat	Kredit portfelini tashkil qiluvchi kreditlarni baholash mezonlarini aniqlash;
2-holat	Tijorat banki kredit portfelining strukturasi aniqlash;
3-holat	Kredit portfeli tarkibidagi o‘zgarishlar sabablarini baholash;
4-holat	Kredit portfelining sifatini aniqlash
5-holat	Bank kredit portfelida ko‘rilishi mumkin bo‘lgan zararlarni qoplash zaxirasini aniqlash

XULOSA VA TAKLIFLAR

Yuqoridagi ma‘lumotlar asosida tijorat banklari kredit portfelini optimallashtirishda asosiy vazifalar sifatida quyidagilarni ko‘rsatishimiz mumkin:

- 1) kredit riski darajasiga ta‘sir ko‘rsatuvchi omillarni aniqlash va ularni baholash;
- 2) kredit portfelini kredit risklari, mijozlar tarkibi va kreditlar tarkibi bo‘yicha optimallashtirish;
- 3) kreditlarni diversifikatsiya qilishni, ularning likvidligini va daromadligini ta‘minlash;
- 4) yaratilayotgan zaxiraning yetarliligini baholash va uni o‘z vaqtida zarur darajada tashkil etib borish;
- 5) qarz oluvchining kreditga layoqatlilik darajasini va uning moliyaviy ahvoli o‘zgarishi ehtimolini aniqlash;
- 6) bankning kredit siyosatini portfelni optimallashtirish vazifalariga moslab ishlab chiqish va bank bo‘linmasi darajasigacha har bir mutaxassis bajarishi kerak bo‘lgan vazifalarni belgilash.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, kredit portfelini tahlil qilish bank tomonidan kredit portfeli tarkibi va uning sifat tarkibi yuzasidan doimiy nazoratni amalga oshirishni taqozo etadi. Hozirgi paytda iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishga yo‘naltirilayotgan bank kreditlar hajmi oshishi, bank kreditlaridan foydalanayotgan turli mulkchilik va xo‘jalik yuritish shaklidagi mijozlar miqdorining ko‘payishi banklar tomonidan berilayotgan kreditlarni oqilona shakllantirish va optimal kredit portfel asosida joylashtirishni taqozo etadi.

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DIALOGIK NUTQ LINGVISTIK TAHLIL OBYEKTI SIFATIDA

Karimova Muqaddas Xamidullayevna,

Rus tili va adabiyoti o'qituvchisi

Annotatsiya: *Dialogik nutq lingvistik tahlil obyekti sifatida tadqiqot uchun bitmas-tuganmas manba hisoblanadi. Ushbu hodisaning ko'p qirraliligi tilshunoslik, psixologiya, sotsiologiya, antropologiya va informatika usullarini birlashtirgan fanlararo yondashuvni talab qiladi.*

Kalit so'z va iboralar: *dialog, kompetensiya, obyektivlik, mulqot, monologik nutq, dialogik nutq, ishtirokchi, kommunikativ muhit.*

Dialogik nutq – bu inson muloqotining dinamik tabiatini aks ettiruvchi lingvistik tahlilning noyob va murakkab obyekti. Monologik nutqdan farqli o'laroq, dialog ikki yoki undan ortiq ishtirokchilarning o'zaro ta'siri bilan tavsiflanadi, bu til hodisalariga boy maxsus kommunikativ muhitni yaratadi.

Dialogik nutq – bu ikki yoki undan ortiq shaxslar o'rtasida to'g'ridan-to'g'ri ifodalar almashinuvi mavjud bo'lgan verbal o'zaro ta'sir shakli. Dialogik nutqning asosiy xususiyatlariga quyidagilar kiradi:

1. Interaktivlik (ma'ruzachi va tinglovchi rollarining doimiy o'zgarishi).
2. Spontanlik (ifodalar ko'pincha nutq paytida shakllanadi).
3. Vaziyatlilik (muloqot konteksti bilan yaqin bog'liqlik).
4. Emotsionallik (suhbatdoshlarning his-tuyg'u va munosabatlarini ifodalash).
5. Noverbal muloqot vositalaridan foydalanish.

Muloqot turli xil faoliyat davomida odamlarning o'zaro ta'sirining asosiy jihati hisoblanadi. Muloqot san'atini o'zlashtirish har qanday sohada muvaffaqiyat qozonishga intilgan kishi uchun zarurdir. Samarali verbal ma'lumot almashish uchun ishtirokchilar nafaqat fikr almashishlari, balki uni to'g'ri talqin qilishlari va o'zaro tushunishni ta'minlash uchun muayyan strategiya hamda taktikalardan foydalanishlari kerak. Muloqot ko'pincha to'g'ridan-to'g'ri o'zaro ta'sirdan tashqarida mavjud bo'lgan va aloqa tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlanadigan faoliyat bilan bog'liq bo'lgan muammo yoki ehtiyoj bilan boshlanadi [Леонтьев А.А., 1999]

Muloqotning ahamiyati uning ikki tomonlama rovida: u nafaqat boshqa faoliyatni osonlashtiradi, balki o'zaro ta'sirning mustaqil shaklidir. Ushbu o'zaro ta'sir odamlarni boshqalarni ishontirish, o'z fikrlarini bildirish yoki yangi bilimlarni olish kabi aniq maqsadlarga intilishni o'z ichiga oladi. Muloqotsiz boshqa faoliyat mumkin emas, chunki u sanoat, tijorat, moliyaviy, ilmiy yoki boshqaruv bo'lsin, insonning barcha harakatlaridan oldin hamrohlik qiladi va ba'zan asosini tashkil qiladi [Введенская Л.А., Павлова Л.Г., Катаева Е.Ю., 2002].

Nutq tabiatan dialogikdir, chunki odatda, har doim kimgadir (tinglovchi yoki so'zlashuvchining o'zi) murojaat qilinadi. Shu nuqtai nazardan, muloqotning eng keng tarqalgan shakli dialog deb ta'kidlanadi. Dialogik muloqotning tabiati so'zlashuvchilar o'rtasidagi munosabatlarga va o'zaro ta'sir atrofidagi o'ziga xos holatlarga qarab o'zgaradi.

Bunga turli munozaralar, jumladan, biznes va tasodifiy, fikr almashish hamda kundalik suhbatlar kiradi. Lingvistik nuqtai nazardan, dialogning barcha shakllari qiziqarli [Румянцева Е.Н., 2015]. “Replikalarning o‘zaro ta’siri, suhbatdoshning ta’siri ostida stimul va reaksiyalarning o‘zgarishi, shuningdek, ikkilanishlar, kamchiliklar va takroriy savollar – ularning barchasi tabiiy muloqotning asl mohiyatiga hissa qo‘shadi” [Баранова Г.А., Земская Е.А., Канападзе Л.А., 1978].

Dialog bo‘yicha tadqiqotlar turli shakllarda bo‘lib, so‘nggi yillarda uning tuzilishiga tobora ko‘proq e‘tibor qaratilmoqda. Tilshunoslar ko‘pincha spontan verbal tilning xususiyatlarini o‘rganadilar, adabiyotshunoslar esa qahramonlarning hikoyasi hamda xarakteri bilan bog‘liq jihatlarni tadqiq etadilar. Dialogning stilistik tahlili uning “mexanizmi”ni o‘rganadi. Muloqotda ma‘lumotlar alohida emas, balki taqqoslash va qarama-qarshiliklar doirasida muhim ahamiyatga ega [Борисова И.Н., 1996]. Ushbu taqqoslash va qarama-qarshiliklar, almashinuv hamda sharhlardagi so‘zlar o‘rtasidagi murakkab semantik munosabatlar bilan birga, kompozitsion tuzilish deb ataladigan hodisani yaratadi.

Dialog nazariyasi lingvistik muammolarning keng doirasi bilan bog‘liq va tilshunoslikdan tashqariga chiqadi. Dialogik nutqni o‘rganish tadqiqotchilar oldiga bir qator vazifalarni qo‘yadi, chunki kommunikativ kontekstni samarali tahlil qilish nafaqat lingvistik, balki muloqot nazariyasini ham talab qiladi. Bunga ishtirokchilarning xabardorligini, atrofdagi sharoitlarni, kommunikativ muhitni va muloqot sheriklarining o‘zaro munosabatlari paytida vaziyat kontekstini hisobga olish kiradi [Валюсинская З.В., 1979].

Xulosa o‘rnida aytish mumkinki, mavzudan qat’i nazar, suhbatdoshning nutqi tinglovchiga uni tushunishga va kerakli effektga ega bo‘lishga qaratilgan bo‘lishi kerak. Suhbat ikkala ishtirokchining intellektual qobiliyatlari, hissiy holati va ijtimoiy mavqeini hisobga olgan holda so‘zlashuvchining subyektiv holatini aks ettirishi kerak.

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DIALOGIK NUTQNING KOMMUNIKATIV TAHLILIGA DOIR

Karimova Muqaddas Xamidullayevna

Rus tili va adabiyoti o'qituvchisi

Annotatsiya: *Dialogning umumiy kommunikativ maqsadi mavzuga va individual dialog almashinuvining boshqa xususiyatlariga ta'sir qiladigan aniqroq vazifalarga bo'linishi mumkin. Ushbu almashinuvlarning o'ziga xos kommunikativ funksiyalari har bir ishtirokchi tomonidan qo'llaniladigan umumiy aloqa strategiyalarining murakkab tuzilishini tashkil qiladi.*

Kalit so'z va iboralar: *dialog, dialogik nutq, lingvistika, kognitiv jarayon, pragmatik tahlil, muloqot, kommunikatsiya jarayoni.*

Dialogik nutq lingvistik tahlilning ko'p qirrali obyekti bo'lib, kompleks yondashuv va fanlararo tadqiqot usullaridan foydalanishni talab qiladi. Muloqotni o'rganish nafaqat lingvistik o'zaro ta'sir mexanizmlarini ochib beradi, balki inson aloqasi asosidagi kognitiv jarayonlarni tushunishga ham hissa qo'shadi [Щерба Л.В., 1915].

Nutqiy vaziyatning shart-sharoiti hamda dialogik nutqda ishtirok etayotgan kommunikatsiya ishtirokchilarining tildan foydalanishining pragmatik stilistik xususiyatlari o'rganila boshladi [Маткаримова А.И., 2021].

Ushbu sohadagi keyingi tadqiqotlar nazariy tilshunoslikning rivojlanishi uchun, shuningdek, odamlar bilan tabiiy muloqotni amalga oshirishga qodir sun'iy intellekt tizimlarini yaratish kabi amaliy vazifalar uchun katta ahamiyatga ega.

Turli kommunikativ sohalarda dialogik nutqni tahlil qilish kontekstga qarab lingvistik o'zaro ta'sirning o'ziga xos xususiyatlarini aniqlashga imkon beradi [Беляева П.А., 2005]. Xususan:

1. Kundalik muloqot (spontanlik va norasmiylikning yuqori darajasi (1); so'zlashuv lug'ati va frazeologik birliklardan faol foydalanish; grammatik normalarni tez-tez buzish (3); noverbal muloqot vositalariga tayanish (4).

2. Ishbilarmonlik kommunikatsiyasi (nutq odobi va rasmiyatchilikka rioya qilish (1); kasbiy terminologiyadan foydalanish (2); dialog strukturasi (kun tartibi, reglament) (3); informatsion funksiyaning fatik funksiyadan ustunligi (4).

3. Ilmiy diskurs (terminologiyaning ilmiyligi) (1); ifodalarning izchilligi va asosiligi (2); hissiy bo'yoqli leksikadan minimal foydalanish (3); savol-javob shaklining aniq tuzilishi (masalan, ilmiy munozaralarda) (4).

4. Pedagogik nutq (ishtirokchilar rollarining assimetriyasi (o'qituvchi-talaba) (1); monologik va dialogik elementlarning kombinatsiyasi (2); fikrlashni faollashtirish uchun savol-javob shaklidan foydalanish (3); nutqni suhbatdoshning bilim darajasiga moslashtirish (4).

Dialogik nutq madaniy kontekst bilan chambarchas bog'liq bo'lib, u quyidagi jihatlarda aks etadi:

1. Madaniy skriptlar (ma'lum bir madaniyatga xos bo'lgan muloqotning barqaror modellari).
2. Tabu mavzulari (turli madaniyat vakillari muloqotda foydalanmaydigan sohalari).
3. Proksemika (muloqotni tashkil etishning madaniy jihatdan aniqlangan normalari).
4. Paralingvistik xususiyatlar (madaniy o'ziga xos imo-ishora, yuz ifodalari, intonatsiyalar).

Texnologiyaning rivojlanishi dialogik aloqa shakllari va xususiyatlariga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatdi. Jumladan:

1. Messedjerlar (xabarchilar) va ijtimoiy tarmoqlar: 1) yozma verbal tilning yangi shakllarini rivojlantirish; 2) noverbal signallarning o'rnini bosuvchi emodzilar (tasvirlar) va stikerlardan foydalanish; 3) guruh suhbatlari (chatlar)da "parallel dialoglar" hodisasi.

2. Videokonferensiyalar: 1) texnik cheklovlarning dialog tuzilishiga ta'siri (kechikishlar, muloqot sifati); 2) noverbal muloqotni video formatga moslashtirish; 3) onlayn guruh muhokamalarini o'tkazish uchun yangi konvensiyalar.

Texnologiyaning rivojlanishi dialogik nutqni o'rganish uchun yangi imkoniyatlar ochadi. Jumladan:

1. Katta ma'lumotlarni tahlil qilish (til qonuniyatlari va tendensiyalarini aniqlash uchun dialogik matnlarning keng ko'lamli korpusini o'rganish).

2. Mashinani o'rganish (dialogning rivojlanishini bashorat qilish yoki uning samaradorligini tahlil qilishga qodir modellarni yaratish).

3. Neyrovizualizatsiya (nutqni ishlab chiqarish va idrok etishning kognitiv mexanizmlarini tushunish uchun dialogik muloqot jarayonida miya faoliyatini o'rganish).

4. Multimodal tahlil (maxsus dasturiy ta'minot yordamida dialogning og'zaki, prosodik va kinesik jihatlarini har tomonlama o'rganish).

Dialogik nutqni lingvistik tahlil qilish natijalari turli sohalarda qo'llaniladi. Xususan: 1. Nutqni avtomatik aniqlash va sintez qilish tizimlarini ishlab chiqish. 2. Ko'proq tabiiy inson-kompyuter interfeyslarini yaratish. 3. Chet tillarni o'qitish metodikasini takomillashtirish. 4. Marketing sohasida muloqot strategiyalarini optimallashtirish. 5. Psixoterapiya va maslahat usullarini ishlab chiqish. 6. Verbal til uchun mashina tarjimai algoritmlarini takomillashtirish.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, dialogik nutq lingvistik tahlil ob'ekti sifatida tadqiqot uchun bitmas-tuganmas manba hisoblanadi. Ushbu hodisaning ko'p qirraliligi tilshunoslik, psixologiya, sosiologiya, antropologiya va informatika usullarini birlashtirgan fanlararo yondashuvni talab qiladi. Ushbu sohadagi keyingi tadqiqotlar muloqotning yangi shakllarining lingvistik me'yorlarga ta'sirini o'rganishga, globallashtirgan dunyoda dialogik o'zaro ta'sirning madaniy xususiyatlarini tahlil qilishga, shuningdek, turli kasbiy va ijtimoiy kontekstlarda samarali muloqotni o'qitishning innovatsion usullarini ishlab chiqishga qaratilgan bo'lishi mumkin.

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STAGES OF DEVELOPMENT OF COMMUNICATION SKILLS IN YOUNG CHILDREN

Nazarova Elvira Narimanovna
Head of the Department of Preschool Education
Puchon University in Tashkent

Abstract: *The article reveals the stages of development of communication skills in young children. The article also examines the neoplasms of communication skills at each age stage, highlights the research of various foreign scientists in the field of developing communication skills at an early age.*

Keywords: *communication, communication skills, early age, non-verbal components of speech, communication.*

The formation of communication skills at an early age is formed in conjunction with the process of mastering non-verbal and verbal components of speech, which in various types of activities are leading at a certain age stage of the child's development, i.e. in emotional communication, subject-practical activities and play.

The basis for the formation of communication skills is joint activity with a child. Communication with an adult leads to an enrichment of the means of communication, which become understandable to both sides in the process of interaction. Communication with peers is also a positive experience for children, since the child does not feel excessive demands on himself in this communication and communicates on equal terms, while experiencing an encouraging feeling for communication. [10.401]

The use of certain communication skills is determined by the stage of development of children's speech as a means of communication.

Stages of development of the need for communication between a child and an adult: 1) the need for adult attention and goodwill; 2) cooperation with an adult appears in a child after mastering arbitrary grasping; 3) the need for adult respect arises against the background of children's cognitive activity; 4) the need for mutual understanding and empathy of an adult arises in connection with the interest of relationships and is conditioned by mastering social norms.

Research evidence suggests that verbal communication arises on the basis of more elementary preverbal forms of communication. From the point of view of neuropsychology and neurophysiology, I.M. Sechenov noted in his works that the onset of development falls on infancy and can only lie in various excitations of the body's receptors. [4.93]

The primary verbal communication system (E.I. Isenina calls proto-language) includes the first cry and crying of an infant, a smile, the direction of gaze, gurgling, gurgling, early babbling, etc. Proto-language consists of gestures, facial movements, manipulations with objects, non-verbal sounds, having a non-verbal basis, which in turn fills the child's speech activity in the first two years of his life. With the advent of verbal language, the system of proto-signs does not disappear, but improves, and the child's vocal development takes place

in parallel. During this period, the child is still at the stage of mastering speech and can communicate with others on a non-verbal level.

A newborn child enters into communication gradually. From 0 to the first month of life, the newborn is still poorly included in the surrounding reality. Crying is a reflex manifestation and has a signaling character, being a biological protective reaction to adverse external influences (lack of heat, food, discomfort from contact with wet diapers). This is due to the fact that by the time of birth, the tactile reaction of the child is highly developed.

Children from the 2nd day of life who have constant contact with their mother cry much less, unlike those who are with their mother only during feeding.[9.256] M.I. Lisina noted that affectionate vocal appeal to the child, tactile contact with him, begins to cause a reaction of concentration and fading from the 2nd week of life. R.Fantz's research has shown that from the first days of life there is a reaction of the child on the mother's face. This is undoubtedly a non-verbal means of communication. An infant's indicative reaction to speech is innate. It can be considered that at this stage the first communicative manifestations are observed. The mother feeds and eliminates uncomfortable conditions, thereby forming socio-communicative and cognitive motivations based on biological needs. Touching, stroking, cuddling, kissing, etc. all these actions are stimuli of moderate intensity, entering the child's central nervous system, become motives for communicative and cognitive activity, voice and speech reactions are stimulated. The child can already establish eye-to-eye contact with an adult.[6.208] A smile arises from direct emotional contact between an adult and a child. And against its background, the child shows separate vowels and guttural sounds.

Psychological studies by L.N. Galiguzova, M.G. Elagina, M.I. Lisina, A.G. Ruzskaya, E.O. Smirnova indicate that by 2 months the child develops situational and personal communication with close adults. At first, hearing the voice of a mother or another adult bending over him, the baby listens, concentrates, as if "freezes" at the sound of a human voice. At the same time, the mother's voice is "recognized" by the baby earlier and better than other voices. The personal motive becomes the leading motive of communication. The child is already looking for an adult with his own eyes, turns to the sound of his voice, notices from afar. The communicative need boils down to the kindness and attention of adults. The means of communication for the baby is the category of expressive expressive and mimic actions (gaze, movements and postures, vocalizations), there is a complex of animation. During the first three months, the nature of movement changes, which leads to the creation of optimal conditions for communicative and cognitive activity. All components of the revitalization complex are inseparable from each other, the child of the first months of life cannot make sounds outside of general motor activity, just as he cannot move his arms and legs, remaining silent.

The period from 3 to 6 months is characterized by the development of auditory and visual skills, the ability to find the source of sound in space, to take toys from the hands of an adult. Walking, at about 4-6 months, becomes "melodious", smooth, it is already possible to distinguish some sounds in it - vocals and consonants, vaguely resembling vowels and

consonants that sound "on exhalation". While walking, a healthy baby expresses his complete satisfaction by "cooing" in the crib for a long time. But as soon as an adult bends over a child, the baby first falls silent, examining the person, and then, if they do not start talking to him or at least smiling, he begins to whimper, protesting against formal communication.

An important point in the development of preverbal communication is that during the period of walking, the child develops the basic skills to distinguish his own "speech" actions from those of other people (Vinarskaya E.N., Bogomazov G.M., 2001). At the same time, the child gradually becomes an active partner of the adult in communication. This period is characterized by the appearance of the first syllabic babble. Babbling develops on the basis of innate unconditioned reflexes (sucking, swallowing and others). With automation, babbling acquires a rhythmic pattern – the sigmatic organization of speech (A.A.Leontiev).

A period of up to 6 months can be characterized as a formative form of behavior. This is a period of imitation. It is characterized by mimic and pantomimic movements – sticking out the tongue, opening and closing the mouth, stretching the lips, various hand movements, imitation of vocalizations and facial expressions of an adult. In the period from 6 to 12 months, the development of the child's behavior becomes more complicated. His interest in the environment increases. Visual, auditory perception, tactile sensitivity are developing, and the activity of the kinesthetic analyzer is becoming more complicated. This happens through groping, tapping, and looking at objects. [7.169]

E.V. Sheremetyeva points out that the use of the pointing gesture occurs, among other things, to satisfy cognitive needs, provided that emotional communication with close adults is formed. During this period of development, the pointing gesture replaces the question "What is it?".

At the end of the first half of the year, the child masters grasping. During this period of time, the following form of communication is emerging - situational and business. This communication is a new type of activity for a child and develops against the background of object manipulation. There is an interest in cooperation, joint action with an adult.

Thus, communication skills become more complicated in the joint activities of an adult and a child. The desire to be with others indicates the strengthening of communicative intentions.

The period is from 9 to 12 months. By the end of the first year of life, visual and auditory reactions become more developed, children recognize a loved one in photographs, react to different music tempos, show great interest in others, begin to isolate individual words from the adult speech stream, assimilate intonation, rhythm and melody of speech. By the end of the first year of a child's life, many words in adult speech acquire a generalized character - "impossible", "bang", etc. It becomes possible to influence his behavior through speech. Babble appears steadily, T.N. Ushakova points to the appearance of "infant conversation-singing" at this age. The baby produces more or less prolonged vocalizations of various affective colors, as if narrating something. It can also be used to satisfy one's desire through a partner (9). The child accumulates a passive vocabulary and forms active

speech, mastering simple words occurs. The basis of the first words is the understanding of speech, the ability to babble and imitate, the first verbalizations appear.

We have considered in detail the first preverbal stage (using the periodization of M.I. Lisina) because, from the point of view of psychology, linguistics and psycholinguistics, it is at this time that the need for communication is formed.

Thus, a child of the first year learns to communicate emotionally with adults, voice reactions develop, an active understanding of adult speech occurs, and the child acquires basic communication skills. He learns to use non-verbal means of communication to achieve his goal, phonemic hearing and speech motor apparatus are formed. Communication with an adult during this period leads to the development of emotional and imaginative perception and is a transitional period to the formation of verbal communication.

Mastering basic communication skills is possible only with the direct participation of adults. In turn, adults should take into account the ontogenesis of the child's development, the stages of development of children's speech, available means of communication, and the child's communication needs with partners.

Communication skills are formed in the constant process of communication between a child and partners, being the foundation for the development of speech skills, which in turn contribute to the development of language skills. The acquisition of new knowledge and skills by a child leads to the enrichment of his consciousness.

Thus, a communicative situation is a stimulus to the need for communication and ensures the development of skills of an early age child. Timely acquisition of communication skills leads to successful socialization and adaptation of an early age child in society.

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MOLIYAVIY INSTRUMENTLAR

Odiljonova Oybarchin Fayzullo qizi.

Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti maqsadli tayanch doktoranti

Iqtisodiy tarixdan ma'lumki, kompaniyalar faoliyatini rivojlantirish maqsadida ko'proq kredit va investitsiyalar instrumentlaridan foydalanib kelgan. Bu trend bugungi kungacha o'z ahamiyatini yo'qotmayotganiga qaramasdan, moliya bozorida alternativ moliyaviy instrumentlar – korporativ qimmatli qog'ozlarni emissiya qilish orqali kapital mablag'larini jalb qilish zarurati paydo bo'ldi. Rivojlangan kapitalistik mamlakatlarda Markaziy bank va hukumat sanoat korxonalarini moliyalashtirmasligi ularning allaqachon yirik korporatsiyalar sifatida fond bozorlarida muntazam ishtirok etishlari asosida faoliyatlarini moliyalashtirishning imkoniyatlarini topganlari bilan izohlanadi.

Umuman olganda qimmatli qog'ozlar tarixi XVII asrga borib taqaladi. 1602 yilda Niderlandiyaning ziravor mahsulotlarni ishlab chiqarish va chakana savdosi bilan shug'ullangan Ost Indiya kompaniyasi o'zining birinchi qimmatli qog'ozlarini – aksiyalarini emissiya qilgan. Aynan shu davrdan boshlab biz bilgan hozirgi qimmatli qog'ozlarning rivojlanish nuqtasi boshlangan. Korporativ qimmatli qog'ozlarning paydo bo'lish tarixi ham aynan shu davrga, birinchi korporatsiya tashkil etilgan davr – XVII asrga borib taqaladi. Bundan kelib chiqadiki qimmatli qog'ozlar dastavval korporatsiyalar (kompaniyalar), undan keyin esa davlat va boshqa xo'jalik yurituvchi subyektlar tomonidan emissiya qilingan. Shunday bo'lsada qimmatli qog'ozlar bozorini ikkita yirik guruh – davlat va korporativ qimmatli qog'ozlar bozori guruhlariga bo'lib o'rganish mumkin.

Korporativ qimmatli qog'ozlar bugungi dunyo fond bozorining eng muhim moliyaviy instrumentlari bo'lib, kompaniyalar aynan ular orqali katta biznes olamiga kirib borishlari mumkin. Xalqaro moliya bozoridagi eng yirik deb hisoblangan NYSE, NASDAQ, SSE, TSE, LSE kabi fond birjalarida eng ko'p savdolar aynan korporativ qimmatli qog'ozlar bilan amalga oshiriladi. Nega aynan korporativ qimmatli qog'ozlar dunyo fond birjalarida muhim moliyaviy instrument ekanligiga uning iqtisodiy mohiyatini tushunish orqali yetish mumkin.

Korporativ qimmatli qog'ozlar faqatgina xo'jalik yurituvchi subyektlar tomonidan muomalaga chiqarilgani uchun ularni qimmatli qog'ozlarning emitentga ko'ra turlari ruknida – xo'jalik yurituvchi subyektlar (AJ, MChJ, kompaniya, korporatsiyalar) tomonidan emissiya qilinadigan qimmatli qog'ozlar turlari hisoblanadi. Xorijiy va mahalliy ilmiy adabiyotlarda korporativ qimmatli qog'ozlarga oid bir qancha nazariy qarashlar mavjud.

Uilyam L. Keri "Federalizm va korporativ huquq: Delaver haqida mulohazalar" (Federalism and Corporate Law: Reflections upon Delaware) nomli ilmiy ishida qimmatli qog'ozlarning korporativ muhitdagi rolini, qimmatli qog'ozlarning korporatsiyalar uchun funkcionalligi va ahamiyati, shuningdek, ularning korxonalarining moliyaviy qarorlariga ta'siri bilan bog'liq mavzularni o'rgangan. Richard A. Brealey, Styuart C. Myers, Franklin Allenlar "Korporativ moliya tamoyillari" (Principles of Corporate Finance) nomli kitobida

korporativ moliyaga keng nuqtai nazardan, jumladan qimmatli qog'ozlar va investitsiyalar nuqtai nazaridan yondashdilar. Ular qimmatli qog'ozlardan foydalanish kompaniyalarning moliyaviy strategiyalariga va kapitalni oshirishga qanday ta'sir qilishi mumkinligini muhokama qilishgan. Ludger Hentschel "Investitsiyalar: Kirish" (Investments: An Introduction) nomli ilmiy ishida korporativ moliya va investitsiyalar bilan bog'liq muammolarni tahlil qilgan hamda korporativ qimmatli qog'ozlarni kompaniyaning investitsiyalarni jalb qilishning eng jozibador usuli sifatida tariflagan. James D. Cox, Robert W. Hillman, Donald C. Langevoort, Ann M. Liptonlarning "Qimmatli qog'ozlarni tartibga solish: keyslar va materiallar" (Securities Regulation: Cases and Materials) nomli ilmiy ishida korporativ moliyaning asosiy elementlarini, shu jumladan korporativ qimmatli qog'ozlar chuqur muhokama qilingan bo'lib, korporativ moliyaviy kontekstda ulardan foydalanish bilan bog'liq mavzularni tahlil qilgan.

Moliyaviy instrumentlar turlari

- Aksiyalar: Aksiyalar kompaniyadagi egalik ulushini ifodalaydi. Aksiyalarni sotib olishda, investorning o'zi biznesning bir qismini egallaydi. Aksiya narxining o'sishi va dividendlar orqali to'lovlar investorlar uchun daromad manbaiga aylanishi mumkin.

- Obligatsiyalar: Obligatsiyalar qo'mita olib boruvchi (hukumat yoki kompaniya) tomonidan chiqariladigan qarz hujjatlaridir. Investorlar imzolagan qarzni kompaniya yoki hukumatga taqdim qiladi va muddat davomida foiz to'lovlarini oladi. Muddatning oxirida, qo'mita olib boruvchi investorning asl qarzini qaytaradi.

- O'zaro fondlar: O'zaro fondlar aktivlar, masalan, aktsiyalar yoki obligatsiyalar to'plamini o'z ichiga olgan boshqariladigan investitsiya vositalaridir. Ular investorlarga imkonini berib, xilma-xil xoldinglarga sarmoya kiritish orqali xavfni kamaytiradi va professional fond menejerlari tomonidan boshqariladi.

- Birja fondlari (ETFlar): ETFlar savdo fondlari kabi savdo-sotiq qilinadigan o'zaro fondlarga o'xshash, asosiy farq shundaki, ular indeksni kuzatish uchun mo'ljallangan va faol ravishda boshqarilmaydi. ETFlar ko'pincha pastroq xarajatlar va ko'proq soliq samaradorligini taklif qiladi.

- Variantlar: Variantlar kelajakda ma'lum vaqtdagi oldindan belgilangan narxda aktivni sotib olish yoki sotish huquqini (majburiyatini emas) beradigan shartnomalardir. Ular spekulatsiya va xedjirlash strategiyalari uchun ishlatilishi mumkin.

- Fyuchers shartnomalari: Fyuchers shartnomalari - bu biror narsani kelajakda oldindan belgilangan narx va sana bo'yicha sotib olish yoki sotish bo'yicha shartnoma hisoblanadi. Ular xam xedjirlash va spekulatsiya uchun ham foydalaniladi.

Investitsiya qilishda xatarni tushunish:

Har qanday moliyaviy vosita bilan bog'liq xatarlar mavjud. Har bir investitsiya turining xatar va daromadlarning o'ziga xos kombinatsiyasi mavjud. O'z xatar bardoshlik darajangizni va investitsiyalaringizni diversifikatsiyalash uchun strategiyani yaratish muhimdir.

Moliyaviy vositalarni qaerdan sotib olish mumkin:

- Brokerlik hisob raqamlari: Onlayn yoki to'liq xizmat ko'rsatuvchi brokerlik firmalari sizga turli xil moliyaviy vositalarni sotib olish va sotish imkoniyatini beradi.

- Robo-maslahatchilar: Robo-maslahatchilar avtomatlashtirilgan investitsiya platformalari bo'lib, ular sizning xatarli xatti-harakatlaringiz va maqsadlaringiz asosida portfel tuzishda yordam beradi.
- Moliyaviy maslahatchilar: Moliyaviy maslahatchilar investitsiya strategiyalarini yaratish va xavfni boshqarishda shaxsiy yordam beradi.

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THE WAYS OF TEACHING ENGLISH VOCABULARY IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS

Abdusattorova Rukhsora Abdurasul of Daughter

Teacher of English at vocational school No. 1, Uychi district, Namangan region

The social order, conditions, and politics of society always determine the work and purpose of a comprehensive school. The goals of teaching foreign languages vary depending on the progress and development of society. In secondary schools, there are goals for teaching foreign languages that affect the correction of the course of foreign language teaching methods and production. In the 40-50s of the last century, the leading goal was to teach listening comprehension in schools, while oral speech was just being formed. And now they change depending on the era, the demands of society. The objectives of teaching a foreign language have their own character, which determines the content, means, methods and principles of teaching.

The main purpose of teaching a foreign language is the practical development of a foreign language. I.V.Rakhmanov mentor L.V. Developing Shcherba's idea, in his article "some issues of teaching a foreign language in secondary schools" he defines the main purpose of teaching a foreign language. He believes that the goals of teaching a foreign language are to create general education, education and communication, as well as to use acquired skills and abilities for other purposes.[1.B.54]. It differs from the goals of communication formation, communicative learning. The very first of the goals of teaching a foreign language is practical. In the methodology of other disciplines, there are educational, educational, developmental goals, a practical goal, i.e. communication is a phenomenon inherent only in foreign languages.

A communicative, communicative, or practical purpose refers to teaching students to perceive the opinions of others verbally and in writing and to express their opinions verbally and in writing.

Thus, teaching foreign languages sets itself the task of: 1) practical or communicative, 2) general education, 3) educational, 4) developmental goal. General education, educational, and developmental goals arise when implementing a communicative goal.[2.B.191]

Now let's focus on each goal separately.

1. Communicative (practical) purpose.

To this end, students develop skills and competencies in English language material. Students should be able to master vocabulary, grammar, pronunciation material on their own. The skills of oral English speech, reading, and writing are being formed.

2. The purpose of providing general education.

This goal is understood as the further development of students' thinking, providing information in English, a deeper understanding of the English language, expanding the horizons of students by gaining new knowledge in the field of English, as well as understanding and information about the history, literature and culture of the people of the

country whose language is amazing. Students' understanding, development of thinking, and broadening of horizons occurs at the expense of a foreign language - English or English.[3.B.90-91]

3. Educational purpose. This goal provides for international, moral and aesthetic education in a foreign language lesson-English, as well as education of attitude to work.

Of course, they are carried out through English language material, analyzing the topic of English speech, the content of English texts.

4. A developmental goal.

This goal defines the ways of learning, teaching students personal knowledge. He develops the skills of linguistic analysis of facts, generalization, independent conclusion, listening, and speech action. It develops imagination, the ability to form speech situations, logical connection in speech, the ability to think independently, the ability to form the meaning of words, independent work with a dictionary, manuals, preparation for elective classes, independent extracurricular English language training, their conduct. The above-mentioned goal always complements each other.[4.B.75]

YANGI TUG'ILGAN CHAQALOQLARDA NEKROTİK ENTEROKOLIT

Foziljon-zoda Maftuna

Samarqand Davlat Tibbiyot Universiteti

Samarqand, O'zbekiston.

Annotatsiya. Nekrotik enterokolit yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloqlarda eng og'ir kasallik hisoblanadi. Nekrotik enterokolitda o'lim o'rtacha 45% ga etadi va ekstremal tana vazniga ega bolalarda peritonit rivojlanishida homiladorlik yoshi 100% gacha kamayishi bilan sezilarli darajada oshadi. Jarrohlar o'rtasida jarrohlik davolash ko'rsatkichlari bo'yicha kelishmovchiliklar mavjud emasligiga qaramay, nekrotik enterokolitning progressiv shakli bo'lgan bemorlarni davolash va jarrohlik taktikasiga yondashuv bugungi kungacha juda ziddiyatli bo'lib qolmoqda.

Tadqiqotning maqsadi. Mahalliy nekroz maydonini va ichak rezektsiyasi darajasini aniqlash usulini ishlab chiqish orqali yarali nekrotik enterokolit bilan og'riqan bemorlarni davolash natijalarini yaxshilash.

Materiallar va usullar. Bu tadqiqot Samarqand Davlat tibbiyot universitetining ixtisoslashtirilgan bolalar jarrohlik klinikasida olib borildi. Ishda NEK tashxisi qo'yilgan 48 bolaning so'nggi 5 yil ichida davolanagan ma'lumotlari mavjud.

NATIJALAR.

69% hollarda (33 bemor) klinik ko'rinish enterokolitning progressiv shakliga to'g'ri keldi, 31% (15 bemor) da ijobiy peritoneal belgilar adinamiya, taxikardiya shaklida sepsisning tizimli ko'rinishlari bilan birgalikda, ya'ni gipotenziya va metabolik atsidozning kuchayishi qayd etildi. 78% (37 bemor) da qorin bo'shlig'i organlarining ultratovush tekshiruvini qalinlashgan devor bilan birlashtirilgan va peristaltikasiz ichak qovuzloqlari konglomeratini aniqladi. Rentgen tekshiruvini o'tkazishda bir nechta gorizontaal suyuqlik darajasi, ichak qovuzloqlarining shishishi va ichak devorining pnevmatozining kuchayishi bilan o'tkir ichak tutilishining odatiy tasviri aniqlandi. Shunday qilib, operatsiyadan oldingi tayyorgarlikdan keyin jarrohlik davolash uchun ko'rsatmalar quyidagi ko'rsatkichlar edi: qorin bo'shlig'ining kengayishi, konservativ choralar bilan bartaraf etilmagan ichak tutilishining klinik ko'rinishi, peritonit, shish, qorin old devorining giperemiyasi, qorin bo'shlig'ining rentgen va ultratovush ma'lumotlari. Ichak nekrozi va teshilish belgilari bilan. Shu bilan birga, og'ir gemodinamik buzilishning rivojlanishi natijasida yuzaga kelgan holatning og'irligi tufayli DIC sindromi belgilari, operatsiyadan oldingi tayyorgarlik 39% hollarda (19 bemor) bemorning ahvolini barqarorlashtirish uchun qorin bo'shlig'ini oldindan drenajlashni o'z ichiga olgan va qorin ichidagi bosimni kamaytirish. Ushbu toifadagi halokatli natijalar 22% (14 bemor). Bemorlarga laparotomiya qilingan. 24% hollarda (12 bemor) qorin bo'shlig'ini yetarli darajada qayta ko'rib chiqish va yangi tug'ilgan chaqaloqdagi ichak qovuzloqlarining hayotiyeligini baholash imkonini beruvchi paraumbilikal kesma qo'llanilgan. Operatsiyadan keyingi davrda enteral ovqatlanishga o'tish jarrohlik aralashuvdan keyingi 5-7-kunlarda amalga oshirildi. Enterostomiyani

yopish uchun rekonstruktiv jarrohlik odatda dastlabki operatsiyadan 3-4 hafta o'tgach amalga oshirildi.

Xulosa. Ushbu tadqiqot natijalari bolalarda yarali nekrotik enterokolitni jarrohlik davolashni yaxshilash imkoniyatini ko'rsatadi. Tadqiqot asosida ishlab chiqilgan va joriy etilgan innovatsion usullar davolash natijalarini yaxshilash, oqibatlar va o'lim sonini kamaytirish imkonini beradi.

TRENDS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN.

Nurillayeva Sevinch Nurmamat kizi

Student of SamDCHTI.

Abstract. *This article talks about the trends and importance of tourism development in our country.*

Key words. *Tourism, economy, industry, eco tourism, food, UN, activity, development, trend.*

Today, it is noted that the tourism industry is one of the fastest growing industries. According to the data, the tourism industry is considered one of the most profitable industries after the automotive industry and oil refining. By developing the tourism industry, it is possible to improve other types of services in the country. In particular, a number of sectors such as transport, food, communication, hotel, construction can be adapted to the world's requirements and through this, quality improvement can be achieved. Also, tourism is a direction with the characteristic of creating many jobs. According to BTT data, every 10 tourists around the world create one job. The development of tourism in Uzbekistan has a positive effect on the country's economy and its place in the world community. By analyzing the development trends of world tourism, it is possible to form modern tourism trends in Uzbekistan and find solutions to existing problems.

Special attention is paid to the role of the tourism sector in the modern economy, in the development of new jobs and small businesses. Modern trends in the development of tourism in the world economy, regions, developed and developing countries are analyzed. Priority directions of tourism development in Uzbekistan, support measures, including the development of transport logistics, infrastructure, hotels, simplification of visa procedures are given great attention. The article examines the characteristics of global, regional and national development of tourism. The modern tourism market, including urban travel, halal tourism, and development trends and prospects of other tourist destinations, including urban travel, halal tourism, pilgrimage tourism, etc., are highlighted.

In the process of globalization, the tourism sector is very important in the economic activity of countries as a sector that brings high income. The role of tourism in developing small business and entrepreneurship, creating jobs, and preserving the culture and traditions of the local people is incomparable. There are more than 7,300 cultural heritage objects in our country, and the fact that most of them are included in the UNESCO list indicates that our country has sufficient potential in the field of tourism. For this reason, a number of reforms are being implemented in Uzbekistan to strengthen the role of this sector in the economy. According to the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 27, 2023 No. PQ-238 "On measures to further accelerate reforms in the field of tourism and effectively organize the state management system in the field" held in.

- From 20 US dollars to 100 US dollars in equal shares at the expense of the State budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Tourism Support Fund for each tourist

brought to the Republic of Uzbekistan from foreign countries with a low tourist flow by tour operators allocating incentive subsidies equivalent to

- Part of the expenses of tour operators and air carriers for charter flights from foreign countries to the international airports of Samarkand, Bukhara and Urganch for each foreign tourist, if he stays at least five nights in the territory of the republic, 20 US dollars, in the winter season (from November 20 to 20 - up to February) to compensate in equal shares from the State Budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Tourism Support Fund equivalent to 50 US dollars;

-Until January 1, 2025, accommodation facilities that do not have a category (star) receive a category three or higher (star), the costs of issuing a certificate of conformity will be covered by the funds of the Tourism Support Fund. ;

-plans such as the training of qualified personnel and the establishment of the involvement of internationally recognized educational programs on the basis of "franchise".

Despite the fact that our country has a place in the world tourist market, the level of creating comfortable conditions for tourists, improving service, increasing the attractiveness of tourist attractions, and strengthening advertising is very low. Therefore, thinking about a significant increase in this regard depends on these factors.

There is no doubt that the head of state's attention to tourism among all other sectors in our country will serve as a program for the rapid implementation of measures to eliminate deficiencies and problems in this sector. As Uzbekistan has its place and importance among countries with great tourism potential, we should use the available opportunities to the maximum.

So far, foreign countries have been lax in promoting more information about Uzbekistan. In particular, most tourists visiting our country today are attracted by tourism companies. In almost all European countries, people do not have enough information about Uzbekistan. They have heard and expressed interest through travel agencies.

The empire of the mighty Mavorunnahr kingdom founded by Amir Temur, a great leader and statesman who made a great contribution to world civilization, became famous throughout the world in the Middle Ages. Therefore, it is the most urgent issue of today to promote the modern beauty and freshness of that kingdom more widely, to strengthen promotion and propaganda work, and to attract more foreign tourists.

Achieving environmental sustainability in tourism is one of the important issues for the whole world. Environmental changes and problems that have been observed in various countries for several years, including the increase in natural disasters, air pollution, outbreak of infectious diseases, are considered as a problem to be solved on a general scale. Such events have a negative impact not only on human health, but also on the country's tourism industry and economy. In addition, several problems are arising in our country. Among these are the drying of the air and the increase in the amount of dust, salt storms, especially in the regions of Karakalpakstan and Khorezm. A number of measures, conferences and programs are being organized around the world in connection with the trend of sustainable tourism development. The main principle of sustainable tourism is to travel consciously for the benefit of nature and local communities.

The tourism industry as a profitable industry occupies an important place not only in the whole world, but also in Uzbekistan. Our country is a region rich in historical, natural resources and opportunities for the formation of various directions of tourism. The rapid growth of the population in Uzbekistan has been an impetus for the development of the country's domestic tourism. Also, many measures are being implemented to achieve sustainable tourism, which is relevant for the whole world. And, of course, because it is full of natural resources, it decided to use the opportunities of ecological tourism wisely. In short, it is one of the important tasks to analyze the existing problems and find a solution to them in establishing modern trends in our country.

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ANALYSIS OF TEXT DESCRIBING CEREMONIES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

Shahobova Sitora Bahromovna

English teacher, Sheikhotokhur specialized school, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Abstract *This article analyzes the fact that texts related to English and Uzbek rituals are often created in an oral artistic form, each of them has its own lexicon, and scientific and popular texts adapted to the transmission of information are also created using these words. Through ritual texts, it was found that the concept of "text" causes problems in translation due to the relationship between language and speech, its multi-functionality, and the expression of hierarchical relations as a multi-layered integration event in terms of structure.*

Key words: *Uzbek and English literature, scientific and popular, culture, relation of speech, component.*

INTRODUCTION

Since the words used in ceremonial texts are related to the social life of the people, their equivalents in other languages do not exist. When translating such words, scientists and translators use more translation methods such as transliteration and commenting. For example, although some errors and omissions were made in the English translations of Uzbek rituals, foreign students were introduced to some information about our national rituals.

The most important type of text is literary text. Also, the texts emphasize learning in a diachronic and synchronic aspect. This indicates that it has ancient, classical and modern types. The texts are also divided into scientific, scientific-popular, and artistic types. From this it is understood that they have artistic and non-artistic forms. The principles of literary text organization are examined to reveal the main differences between such texts. Fiction is studied through the method of linguopoetic research. In this, the main attention is paid to the creator's worldview, emotional-modal attitude to reality, originality of creative thinking, language.

The main rules of the theory of the artistic text are that it is based on the figurative perception of the world. It is known that artistic texts are created in poetic, prose, dramatic form.

The organization of an artistic text is characterized by its own complexity and multifunctionality, it actively uses aspects and levels that are not loaded in other types of speech communication and become insignificant, as a result of which the structure of an artistic text has a multi-layered structure. It is combined with a unique hierarchical relationship between the layers, which often requires great creative effort on the part of the translator.

Main part: Ritual texts have an aesthetic value. Although they were originally created as a text by one author, then as a result of word of mouth, from generation to generation, they become texts created by many different authors. Ceremonial texts are the subject of

research of many researchers as a phenomenon of language and speech, a product of people's poetic thinking. In the ritual texts, the authors have the opportunity to verbally convey their attitude to some real reality or religious belief.

As we have seen above, concepts related to ceremonies are decoded through words expressing their attributes. A number of hermeneutic indicators are added to the ritual text and its subtext content. In the texts related to the ceremony, the names of folk customs, paintings and drawings attract attention due to the frequent use of the names *lingvokul'turema* (words reflecting culture), *ethnographisms* (words reflecting the people's life), therefore, in understanding them it is necessary to work in connection with cultural studies, ethnography, dialectology. Whether scientific or scientific-popular texts explaining ceremonies or artistic texts serving to increase their effectiveness are created, in which lexical-semantic and stylistic units and syntactic devices are used to express the concepts related to them. Such hermeneutic indicators, which have an unlimited scope, are filled with new components. These indicators are often lexical and are described and interpreted in large and small contexts. Such lexical signals are important in conveying information about the status, structure, purpose, and tasks of a certain ceremony.

Text performer (singer, puppeteer, singer, etc.); text listener (people). By studying the relationship between them, the position of using the text becomes clear. Because the representatives of the people pay special attention to the signals of their point of view, look for and use the text of the ceremony. It repeats fragments of ritual texts in compositionally juxtaposed forms (sound, word, phrase, sentence), actualization of synsemantic words, title, etc.

In some such texts, a situation of objective assessment of the surrounding world and surrounding events is observed. In them, the narrator is the third person. Texts are also aimed at learning different types of speech. Depending on them, it is possible to distinguish political, mass-informational, business, scientific, pedagogical, religious, medical, memoir, personality-oriented and other types of speech. Using the language, texts can play the role of a reliable object in understanding the organization of speech, the classification and development of the language. Syntagmatic and paradigmatic connections in the text, harmony of universal ideas, integrity, situationality, special superphrase units with denotative unit signs are fully interpreted.

So, the text is a multidimensional phenomenon consisting of a sequence of linguistic signs, which is united on the basis of meaning, has consistency and integrity. Therefore, a text can be considered in semiotics as a sequence of any sign units, and in the framework of linguistic semiotics, it is correct - as a sequence of oral or written verbal signs. Studying the text includes not only functional, but also pragmatic aspects.

Conclusion: By now, texts have become objects of research. As a result, it is important that text analysis (textual analysis), textual studies find a separate and wide development. This shows that according to the creation of the text, whether it is oral or written, it is diachronic and synchronic. It is observed that the texts are large and small, prose, poetic, dramatic, and mainly perform the task of providing information. They differ from each other in that they are scientific, artistic, journalistic in spirit. The source of intertextuality as an

interaction of meaning-creating structures can be the cultural (primarily literary and artistic) and socio-historical context. In post-folklore, ritual intertexts are emerging, which can sometimes be understood through the use of "foreign" words in the texts. The text should be taken as complete information and systematic integrity. Text types are diverse and each has its own characteristics.

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